

OpenRRIHub Network

DEVELOPING TERRITORIAL RRI GOVERNANCE

List of participants

CONSORTIUM	ACRONYM	COUNTRY	ROLE
Universiteit Leiden (P1 – Project Coordinator)	ULEI	NL	RRI expert & Territorial Partner
The Provost, Fellows, Foundation Scholars and the other members of Board, of the College of the Holy and Undivided Trinity of Queen Elizabeth near Dublin – Science Gallery Dublin and School of Education (P2)	TCD	IE	RRI expert
Qualia Analytics (P3)	QA	IE	RRI expert
Impact Hub Siracusa (P4)	IHS	IT	RRI expert
Science Now (P5)	SN	PL	RRI expert
Municipality Figueira de Castelo Rodrigo (P6)	MFCR	PT	Territorial partner
AIR Centre / Regional Government of Azores (P7)	AIRC	PT	Territorial partner
Government of Aruba / Futura Lab (P8)	FL	AW	Territorial partner

Table of Contents

1. Excellence	3
1.1. Objectives	4
1.2. Relation to the work programme	8
1.3. Concept and methodology; quality of the measures	11
1.3.1. Overall Concept	11
1.3.2. National or international research and innovation activities which are linked with the project	14
1.3.3. Methodology	15
1.3.4. OpenRRIHub Gender Equality Dimension	17
1.3.5. Track record implementing RRI processes by the OpenRRIHub partners	17
2. Impact	19
2.1. Expected impacts	19
2.1.1. Short term impact: 0-3 years	20
2.1.2. Short term impact: 0-3 years & Medium term impact: 3-5 years	22
2.1.3. Long-term impact: 5 – 10 years	24
2.2. Measures to maximise impact	26
2.2.1. Dissemination and exploitation of results	27
2.2.2. Communication activities	30
3. Implementation	32
3.1. Work plan – Work packages and deliverables	32
3.2. Management structure and procedures	45
3.2.1. Organisation structure and decision-making	45
3.2.2. Risk mitigation	47
3.3. Consortium as a whole	48
3.4. Resources to be committed	48

1. Excellence

The 21st century is becoming increasingly defined by the need to respond to major social, environmental and economic challenges, the so-called “grand challenges”, which include climate change, demographic challenges, and promotion of health and wellbeing. These problems are ‘wicked’ in the sense that they are complex, systemic, interconnected, and urgent; requiring attention to the ways in which social issues interact with political and technological issues, behavioural changes, smart regulation, and critical feedback processes. For example, poverty cannot be tackled without attention to the interconnections between nutrition, health, infrastructure, and education, as well as redistributive tax policy. The COVID-19 pandemic currently the world is facing is also a remarkable example of the complexity of these systemic issues.

Innovation is a key driver of long-term growth and it has also benefited from social movements putting pressure on systems to change. Indeed, some of the greatest innovations of our time, mainly technological (like the internet or GPS), have come from the need to solve problems. Now is the time to focus innovation efforts to solve societal challenges that involve technological change, institutional and behavioural change and regulatory change. Grand challenges by their nature are big, bold, difficult and complex. So, in order to make these challenges achievable, they have to be broken down into pragmatic steps – into missions – , concrete targets within a challenge that act as frames and stimuli for innovation, as has been defined in the report Mission-Oriented Research & Innovation in the European Union¹.

The Open Responsible Research and Innovation Hub (OpenRRIHub) network will establish Grand Challenge knowledge broker teams – OpenRRIHubs – in governmental structures to tackle relevant societal challenges using a Mission-oriented approach. The OpenRRIHub teams will operate across sectors, drawing policy expertise from across government departments and bringing technical know-how and expertise from a broad R&I infrastructure formed by other members of the Quadruple Helix (QH). For that, 4 OpenRRIHubs will be created in communities that traditionally do not engage with R&I or do not bring RRI dimensions into the R&I processes due to various barriers (geographical location, socio-economic status, or minority ethnic group background). The OpenRRIHubs consortium brings a solid and comprehensive team, formed by 2 complementary categories of partners:

A) Territorial Partners with strong knowledge of their territories and respective physical, economical and social ecosystems, where three of the partners are governmental institutions:

- Local (Municipality in a rural area in Portugal; P6-MFCR)
- Regional (regional government of Azores islands; P7-AIRC)
- National (national government of Aruba; P8-FL)
- One university with formal links with local municipalities and developing several projects focused on science & society (Center for Entrepreneurship and Innovation: Leiden University – Municipality of Leiden – Municipality of the Hague; P1-ULEI);

B) RRI Experts – 2 Universities and 3 SMEs – with a wide and proven track record of implementing RRI processes both at governmental, academic, industry, and civil society levels (P1-ULEI; P2-TCD; P3-QA; P4-IHS; P5-SN).

The OpenRRIHubs approach resonates with the dynamics of the 21st century. Through cross-sectoral mission-oriented processes and open stakeholder engagement, Open RRI Hubs provide an opportunity to tackle relevant societal challenges, by implementing a more open and transparent R&I System in their defined territories, and ultimately leading to institutional change in governmental structures, empowering communities to tackle relevant issues and helping to reduce socio-economic, gender, regional and other disparities².

OpenRRIHub is designed to contribute to SwafS programme strategic orientation 3: Building the territorial dimension of SwafS partnerships. We do this by developing new partnerships at the territorial level to co-create, co-implement and co-assess Grand Challenge-driven Missions. These partnerships will include universities, formal and non-formal education institutions (including primary and secondary schools, science museums and centres), governments and public authorities (including regional and local administrations), businesses (including industry, SMS, and the service sector) and CSOs operating at local, national and European levels. OpenRRIHubs represent a new way to foster mutual learning between policy, research and practice, and to open up R&I to society at the territorial level, catalyzing positive change in society. These will take into account specific regional needs and contexts, ensuring the involvement of communities in different territorial contexts (e.g. rural vs. urban areas), alongside the promotion of gender equality (and wider intersectional diversity), and consideration and involvement of all people, irrespective of their age, gender, ethnicity and socio-economic background.

1 Mazzucato, M. (2018), Missions: Mission-Oriented Research & Innovation in the European Union. European Commission. Available online at https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/mazzucato_report_2018.pdf

2 European Commission (2007). The European Research Area: New Perspectives: Office for Official Publications of the European Communities. Luxembourg

OpenRRIHub's distinctive contribution

At the outset, we would like to highlight how OpenRRIHub makes a special contribution that takes account of its timing at the end of the SwafS funding programme cycle:

Highlights of our approach:

- Leveraging location in the final cycle of SwafS-14 funding by ensuring that established best practice from current and past SwafS-14 projects is integrated into our work to enhance impact.
- Establishing syntheses of best practice that can form part of the long-term legacy of SwafS-14, providing a library of resources about RRI integration into regional R&I ecosystems. This will make the learnings of SwafS-14 easily accessible to projects in Horizon Europe and beyond.
- As part of the project's efforts to create a bridge between SwafS-14 and Horizon Europe, OpenRRIHubs will focus on the Horizon Europe missions, which will be co-created, co-implemented and co-assessed in each Territorial Partner location.
- Range of partners and their locations enables inter-cultural engagement and mutual learning across a diverse range of countries from Europe and beyond.
- RRI Expert Partners, that bring deep expertise and experience in RRI and regional R&I ecosystem interventions, including experience in dozens of SwafS projects (Table 1.4): Leiden University, The Netherlands (P1); Trinity College Dublin, Ireland (P2); Qualia Analytics, Ireland (P3); Impact Hub Siracusa, Italy (P4); Science Now, Poland (P5). This increases the probability of operational success, while ensuring that partners are able to 'hit the ground' running in this project.
- Building durable structures for territorial RRI integration that are designed to outlast the project and be maintained as permanent features in the partner countries.
- An evidence-based approach to territorial RRI integration (see Jensen & Gerber, 2020). This is a distinctive feature of our approach, using the best available evidence from across all preceding SwafS-14 projects. We will integrate real-time impact evaluation, using digital evaluation tools, to enable adaptations while the implementation is in progress. This is essential given that this is the final round of SwafS funding, and therefore the project needs to be self-contained to a greater extent than previous projects in the sense of ensuring that learning is fed back into this project as it unfolds.
- To ensure that the project's impact is embedded in the partner organisations, there is a robust impact evaluation that builds on methodological development in two earlier SwafS-14, and another SwafS project in which the lead evaluation partner is currently involved (TeRRIFICA, RRING, GRRIP). This also includes frameworks of Key Performance Indicators developed as part of the RRING project in collaboration with UNESCO.
- The following strategies and plans will be implemented and followed:
 - Gender Equality Strategy Framework learning from GEAR in particular
 - Change Management Plans across all management levels and departments for organisational and cultural change including top Management support guidelines
 - Sustainability strategy for OpenRRIHub actions and activities.
- OpenRRIHubs will strengthen and complement the RRI-related infrastructure of the diverse set of nations that are participating in the project, while yielding resources that can inform the efforts of other nations, inside and outside of the EU.
- OpenRRIHubs integrate gender equality and intersectional considerations into the core of its work and deliverables (defined as gender equality for women and sexual minorities (LGBTQ+)).

1.1. Objectives

Overall, the vision of OpenRRIHubs is to address and generate solutions to societal challenges by setting a mission-oriented approach, through collaborations among policy makers, enterprises, research institutes, and civil society. This will lead to a more open, transparent and R&I System at the territorial level, and empower communities to tackle relevant issues to help reduce socio-economic, gender, regional and other disparities. For that, this project will establish Grand Challenge knowledge brokers teams – OpenRRIHubs – in governmental structures, that will operate across sectors, drawing policy expertise from across government departments and bringing technical know-how and expertise from a broad R&I infrastructure formed by other members of the QH.

OpenRRIHub main objectives tackle the range of call challenges during a 36-month period.

01. Establish and train multidisciplinary Grand Challenge teams – OpenRRI-Hubs – that enable cross-sectoral mission strategy coordination between executive power offices, government departments and quadruple helices (government, academia, industry and civil society).

The OpenRRIHubs work as knowledge brokers that facilitate processes to foster mutual learning among research, policy and practice, with the goal of catalyzing positive change in society. As such, OpenRRIHubs must operate across sectors, drawing policy expertise from across government departments and bringing technical know-how and expertise from a broad research and innovation infrastructure formed by other members of the QH (academia, industry, and civil society).

The establishment of the OpenRRIHubs will involve an RRI Needs Assessment to identify barriers and challenges to the participation of local, regional and national governments in developing institutional and cultural change processes to embed RRI. This RRI Needs Assessment will evaluate each institution's current RRI maturity level, barriers and opportunities.

02. Address and generate solutions to societal challenges by setting ambitious missions across sectors, actors and disciplines, rooted in RRI and evidence-based decision-making through collaborations among policy makers, enterprises, research institutes, and civil society.

OpenRRIHubs will work with the respective governmental structures and local stakeholders to identify relevant key societal challenges, which will be broken down into concrete cross-sectoral missions. The report for the European Commission "Mission-Oriented Innovation Policy: Challenges and Opportunities"³ sets out a framework for developing missions – mission "roadmaps" (Figure 1.1), which explores five criteria: be bold, inspirational with wide societal relevance; set a clear direction that is targeted, measurable and time-bound; be ambitious but not unrealistic; be cross-disciplinary, cross-sectoral and cross-actor innovation; involve multiple, bottom-up solutions.

Each Territorial Partner will identify, grade and rank their relevant societal challenges to design their missions. This will be achieved through RRI-based co-creation, co-design, co-implementation, and co-evaluation processes, representative of citizen concerns, and involving policy makers, enterprises, research institutes, and civil society.

03. Systemically support a dynamic R&I System based on the development of STEAM-based research programmes focused on the grand challenges and missions and support the funding of innovative, cross-sectorial pilot projects to address the defined missions

Missions must be measurable and will be targeted through STEAM-based research and innovation projects which will be framed in a cross-sector manner, bringing in multiple actors. As an example, a Clean Growth mission would not just involve the renewables sector, but most likely also transport, construction, ICT, agriculture, civil society and media. OpenRRIHubs will facilitate the processes from mission-oriented policies to the development of mission-oriented projects, by bringing together policy makers, enterprises, research institutes and civil society and supporting the funding of innovation pilot projects in each OpenRRIHub location.

04. Develop and sustain the engagement of quadruple helices and citizens in each local OpenRRIHub to ensure effective participation in the process and local 'ownership' of the project through training and mentoring

OpenRRIHubs will design and implement targeted training and mentoring workshops for stakeholder groups with defined learning outcomes led by expert member organisations of the consortia on the different RRI Keys (gender equality, societal/public engagement, governance, open access, ethics, science education) and their integration into the norms, processes and goals of the institutions and societal groups within the QHel, in order to achieve O1, O2 and O3.

In addition, best practice in stakeholder engagement will be applied including creating mutual learning processes and sustainable engagement structures within the OpenRRIHubs to foster a healthy R&I ecosystem of open and inclusive practices and policies, which will help to ensure effective participation in the process and a sense of local ‘ownership’ of the project⁴. The consortium partners have extensive experience in RRI processes and stakeholder engagement, as shown in Table 1.4. The design of these programmes will underpin a critical review of training materials from EU (and beyond) previous and current RRI related projects designed to support institutional change pertaining to RRI.

05. Enhance cooperation within and across communities across social and geographical borders in Europe and beyond and empower broader relevant local, national, and international communities through mutual learning and OpenRRIHub methodologies, resources and approaches.

OpenRRIHubs will be created in communities that traditionally do not engage with R&I or do not bring RRI dimensions into the R&I processes due to various barriers (geographical location, socio-economic status, or minority ethnic group background). By bringing together local stakeholders from across the QH categories – schools, families, research institutes, enterprises, industry, civil and wider society – OpenRRIHubs will contribute to equipping the government structures, local stakeholders and communities of the Territorial Partners with the tools and networks they need to address societal challenges where R&I can help. This objective involves developing a mutual learning process across the participating territories, including periodic structured sharing calls during the implementation with rotating chairs (maintaining gender balance and regional diversity in leadership of mutual learning). To encourage usage and maximise impact, in Europe and beyond, all resources, products and solutions developed by OpenRRIHub will be fully based on Open Standards and Horizon 2020 guidelines on open access. OpenRRIHub expertise, resources, and best practices will be shared through the creation of OpenRRIHub online platform as well as on existing large online repositories and relevant national networks and repositories. This mutual learning process will be subject to ongoing evaluation feedback loops to ensure that the meetings are delivering useful insights for partners and that there is effective communication in general. To extend mutual learning to empower wider regional R&I stakeholders, each OpenRRIHub will organise continuing professional development workshops at regional and national events.

06. Develop legacy and sustainability plans to ensure continuous development of the OpenRRIHubs and of the R&I System beyond the duration of the project, by establishing partnerships with the public and private sectors

Each OpenRRIHub will be supported to develop a sustainable financial plan in collaboration with local partners, where Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental, Social and Governance⁵ approaches with the private sector will be encouraged. To ensure continuous development of the OpenRRIHub beyond the duration of the project, an assessment will be conducted to identify potential sources of funding and partnerships both in public and in private sectors, encompassing relevant governments (local, regional, or national), industries, trade unions, SMEs, and professional and sectoral associations. Business development kits will be delivered to new OpenRRIHub teams from which each individual OpenRRIHub will tailor their own business model, suitable for their own region and community’s specific characteristics. These kits will involve RRI framework templates and guidelines for local, regional and national governments.

07. Contribute to the SwafS legacy and synthesise SwafS knowledge base in territorial RRI to build long-term capacity

To exploit the insights and knowledge gained from the implementation of this project, a sustainable capacity-building tool will be developed to provide a SwafS14-wide legacy synthesising learning from across all SwafS14 projects for the benefit of territorial scholars, students and policy-makers. It will be designed with several entry points and learning pathways for heterogeneous audiences with diverse interests and professional needs, as well as cultural backgrounds and language requirements.

4 http://ec.europa.eu/education/news/2015/documents/citizenship-education-declaration_en.pdf

5 <https://www.robecosam.com/en/key-strengths/esg-research.html>

Figure 1.1: Mission-oriented approach: from Challenges to Missions and Projects⁶

Figure 1.2: OpenRRIHubs relations within governmental Institutional Structures (adapted from UCL Commission for Mission-Oriented Innovation and Industrial Strategy)⁷

6 https://www.ucl.ac.uk/bartlett/public-purpose/sites/public-purpose/files/190515_iipp_report_mois_final_artwork_digital_export.pdf

7 https://www.ucl.ac.uk/bartlett/public-purpose/sites/public-purpose/files/190515_iipp_report_mois_final_artwork_digital_export.pdf

1.2. Relation to the work programme

OpenRRIHub proposal directly addresses all key challenges identified by the work programme call *Supporting the development of territorial Responsible Research and Innovation*. Table 1.1 summarises OpenRRIHub solutions and approaches to tackle the challenges and meet the project objectives.

Table 1.1. Key challenges identified by the work programme and respective OpenRRIHub Solutions.

KEY CHALLENGES IDENTIFIED BY THE WORK PROGRAMME	OPENRRIHUB SOLUTIONS
<p><i>[...] encourage societal actors to work together during the whole research and innovation (R&I) process to better align R&I and its outcomes with the values, needs and expectations of society.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S1: Establishment and training of multidisciplinary Grand Challenge teams – OpenRRIHubs – that enable the coordination of the mission-oriented strategies and respective projects between executive power offices, government departments and quadruple helices (government, academia, industry and civil society). • S2: Involvement of the local societal actors, including citizens, in defining and setting the Grand Challenge-driven Missions, through RRI-based co-creation, design, implementation and evaluation processes. • S3: Support the funding of cross-sectorial and multidisciplinary STEAM-based research and innovation pilot projects to address the identified Missions, through an open call process, where the selection committee will be composed by policy makers, professionals from enterprises, research institutes, civil society and citizens. • S4: Encourage and support the involvement of the QH local actors throughout the implementation and assessment phases of the Mission-oriented R&I projects through periodic (every 6 months) sessions aimed at strengthening the alignment between R&I processes and outcomes with societal needs and expectations. • S5: Development and implementation of continuing professional RRI development programmes for local stakeholder groups, to share methodologies, resources and approaches. • S6: Establishment of a project Advisory Board (AB), where each AB member will be selected for a special relevant expertise, including coordination with research institutes, enterprises, industry, civil society organisations, local governments and wider society (including families); gender & diversity balance; and establishment of local OpenRRIHub Management Boards (MBs), with representatives from different QH societal stakeholders, which will be involved in all key processes and decisions of OpenRRIHubs. • S7: Establishment of OpenRRIHubs in communities that traditionally do not engage with RRI due to various social/geographical barriers, widening access and enhancing cooperation across cultures and communities.
<p><i>(2) Territories have a specific advantage to address the complexity of the challenges set by the interplay between science and society. Local actors have intimate knowledge of the physical territorial setting, and local ecology.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S8: The OpenRRIHubs consortium is formed from 2 complementary categories of partners: A) Territorial Partners with strong knowledge about their territories and respective physical, economical and social ecosystems – local (P6-MFCR), regional (P7-AIRC) and national governments (P8-FL), and a university with formal connections with local municipalities and several projects focused on science & society (P1-ULEI); B) RRI Experts with wide and proven experience implementing RRI processes both at governmental, academic, industry, and civil society levels (P1-ULEI; P2-TCD; P3-QA; P4-IHS; P5-SN).
<p><i>Local and regional authorities should be active partners of the consortia, in particular those institutions or parts of institutions responsible for research and innovation, alongside organisations representing the other parts of the quadruple helix.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S9: Creation of partnership networks between local actors which will be involved throughout the several steps of the project, from mission-design to R&I project development, implementation, evaluation and communication: citizens and civil society organisations (CSOs), universities, research institutions, formal and non-formal education institutions (including schools, musea, science and cultural centres), governments and public authorities (including regional and local administrations and science policy institutions), businesses and SMEs (including industry, the service sector and social entrepreneurs) and science mediators in the context of RRI programmes.

*[...] Since 2010, the Commission has encouraged regions to develop smart specialisation strategies, based on **comprehensive stakeholder involvement**, to identify fields of industrial & research strengths with potential for competitive advantages.*

(3) New R&I working methods within and between organisations, including novel and transparent governance relations, would promote greater sustainability and inclusiveness at local, national, EU and global levels.

[...] a view to developing and promoting shared learning and diffusion of governance innovations.

(4) The RRI approach should be integrated in regional development policies, e.g. spatial planning, land use planning, coastal planning, urban development and urban structuring activities

(9) “Consortia should make strong efforts to ensure the involvement of all kind of citizens, irrespective of their age, gender, ethnicity and socio-economic background.”

- S10: To ensure that best practice will guide the approach to stakeholder engagement, a review of outputs and templates from prior EU funded projects will be conducted, along with a literature review narrowly focused on identifying best practice. This work will feed into a strategic plan for successful stakeholder and wider citizen engagement for each region will be developed, refined through feedback sessions with local partners and published.
- S11: Empirical assessment of stakeholder expectations, hopes and concerns relevant to the project at an early stage of the project to lay the groundwork for local QH ownership of the innovative approaches proposed.
- S12: By implementing S1 and considering S8, OpenRRIHubs will incentivise and support organisations to collaborate in fundamentally new ways – across the state, businesses and civil society, and to build symbiotic and open ecosystems that will deliver sustainable public value.
- S13: OpenRRIHubs will be fully based on the H2020 Guidelines on Open Access, and on Open Standards, processes, protocols or resources which will be made available to societal actors and to the general public, and developed and maintained via a collaborative and consensus driven process⁸, thus promoting sustainable transparent governance relations.
- S14: OpenRRIHubs will support the funding of cross-sectoral, bottom-up STEAM-based R&I pilot projects, to address the Grand Challenge-driven Missions; these projects will be selected based on open stakeholder participation and considering citizen values and needs.
- S15: Convene mutual learning meetings between project partners, and document ‘lessons learned’ along the way, both at the level of OpenRRIHub network and local stakeholders to, e.g. identify common challenges and opportunities across the different local OpenRRIHubs, to establish institutional learning and share insights with other ongoing EU projects.
- S16: OpenRRIHubs will establish evidence-based QH Open and Inclusive Support Structures that will integrate the institutional structure of the Territorial Partners. Since OpenRRIHubs will be multidisciplinary and boundary-crossing (S1), these working methods will lead to institutional changes in other groups/departments/stakeholders, reinforced through a continuing professional RRI development program (S5), including capacity building activities.
- S17: As mentioned in S8, Territorial Partners consist of local (P6-MFCR), regional (P7-AIRC) and national governments (P8-FL) and a university with formal connections with local municipalities (P1-ULEI).
- S18: Develop, tailor/adapt individual RRI Action Plans for territorial R&I ecosystems with specific focus on their missions and stakeholder context.
- S19: Training of OpenRRIHub partners and local OpenRRIHubs teams on gender equity programming, to be able to analyse and consider how groups, procedures and the focus on innovation may limit women’s participation and to provide activities that are inclusive and equitable for all genders and orientations, as well as on diversity inclusion.
- S20: Support consortium members and collaborators with caring-responsibilities by ensuring meetings at family-friendly hours, and facilitating family-friendly working arrangements within all partner organisations.
- S21: Consideration of gender balance in OpenRRIHub programme – including invitees and participants, project AB, local OpenRRIHubMBs, and OpenRRIHub local teams.
- S22: Assignment of a dedicated member of the AB to monitor the gender dimension of OpenRRIHub.
- S23: Supporting linguistic variety across border regions and groups (including minority and migrant groups) by ensuring representation of local linguistic variety in OpenRRIHub teams, and by making available OpenRRIHub resources in several languages (at least, English, Dutch, Italian, Polish, Portuguese and Papiamentu).

(5) [...] lay out a sequence of actions that open up and transform the R&I ecosystem and governance systems so that they are more open and inclusive.

- Solutions/approaches mentioned previously: S12, S13, S14, S15, S16
- S24: Use of Open Standards – open architecture, open education, open technology, and open science – to share and disseminate OpenRRIHub products, knowledge and processes (activities, publications, research, data, and resources) across stakeholders and citizens.

(6) Map their current territorial R&I ecosystem, taking into account and complementing existing mapping exercises such as the Smart Specialisation Platform, the European Cluster Observatory, and the Regional Innovation Scoreboard

- S25: RRI Needs Assessments will be conducted to identify barriers and challenges in participating local, regional and national governments in developing institutional and cultural change processes to embed RRI. This RRI Needs Assessment will evaluate each institution's current RRI maturity level, barriers and opportunities.

(7) Reflect on how the system could be more open and inclusive,

- Solutions/approaches mentioned previously: S12, S13, S14, S15, S16, S19, S20, S21, S22, S23, S24.

(8) Consider their place within larger societal, geographical, economic and environmental framework.

- S26: OpenRRIHubs will tackle societal challenges by setting ambitious missions and coordination R&I projects that work across sectors, actors and disciplines, rooted in RRI and evidence-based decision-making through collaborations among policy makers, enterprises, research institutes, and civil society.
- Solutions/approaches mentioned previously: S1, S2, S4, S9, S10, S18, S25.

(9) develop concrete actions within individual beneficiaries' organisations (e.g. agenda setting and institutional changes in the fields of gender, ethics, public engagement, science education and open access) and in the territorial context (e.g. local and regional governance relations and decision-making processes).

- Solutions/approaches mentioned previously: S1, S2, S4, S9, S13, S14, S16, S18, S19, S24, S25.
- S27: Critically review EU (and beyond) previous and current RRI related projects that were designed to deliver and support institutional change pertaining to RRI to learn from both successes and failures in their prior experience and provide a base of materials to apply to the present project.
- S28: Expert support provided by project partners on implementation of the different RRI Keys.

(10) Changes should be sustainable (last beyond lifetime of funding), for instance through introduction of new forms of decision-making, development of business plans, cooperation agreements and institutional changes in participating organisations.

- Solutions/approaches mentioned previously: S1, S2, S4, S9, S13, S14, S16, S18, S19, S24, S25.
- S29: Develop legacy and sustainability plans to ensure continuous development of the OpenRRIHubs and of the R&I System beyond the duration of the project, by establishing partnerships with the public and private sectors.

(11) The actions should avoid duplicating the analytical and data collection activities of the Smart Specialisation Platform. Previous project findings and good practices should be considered

- S30: Documents from existing SwafS-14 projects and beyond will be reviewed to identify best practice, latest insights from SUPER-MORRI project and other work on RRI indicators will be synthesised to create an RRI institutional change evaluation framework.

1.3. Concept and methodology, quality of the measures

1.3.1. Overall Concept

The role of RRI for the development of underserved territories and for breaking geographical and social borders and barriers.

The European Territorial Cooperation Regulation⁹ states that ‘Cross-border cooperation should aim to tackle common challenges identified jointly in the border regions, [...] and aim to exploit the untapped growth potential in border areas, while enhancing the cooperation process for the purpose of the overall harmonious development of the Union.’ To achieve this, OpenRRIHub will establish Grand Challenge knowledge broker teams – OpenRRIHubs – in governmental structures to tackle relevant societal challenges. These will use a Mission-oriented approach, in areas that traditionally do not engage with R&I or do not bring RRI dimensions into the R&I processes due to various barriers (geographical location, socio-economic status, or minority ethnic group background). A needs assessment to identify these barriers and challenges faced by local, regional and national governments in developing institutional and cultural change processes to embed RRI into environmental decision-making will be conducted. The OpenRRIHub locations are as follows: Leiden/The Hague – the Netherlands (host of the EuroScience Open Forum 2022, P1-ULEI), Município de Figueira de Castelo Rodrigo – Portugal (rural Municipality; P6-MFCR), Azores – Portugal (Regional Government; P7-AIRC), Aruba – the Netherlands (National Government; P8-FL).

OpenRRIHub Framework

OpenRRIHub will develop a common framework, procedures and templates to be adopted by local OpenRRIHubs, without compromising autonomy and innovation in each location. It will be the core to which all experience and information will flow to be openly used by everyone in and outside of the network. It will also foster mobility and cooperation between OpenRRIHubs and their local partners, enabling pan-European projects and shortening inequalities between communities. Below, we describe the structure and packages that constitute the OpenRRIHub.

1) Identify best practices on building open, democratic and inclusive R&I processes and ecosystems: To inform the development of effective interventions, OpenRRIHub will start by building a knowledge base and guidelines on RRI territorial implementation best-practices. This includes a synthesis review of best practice on RRI institutional change indicators to create an RRI institutional change evaluation framework, as well as a synthesis review of effective strategies for stakeholder engagement at territorial level to develop a stakeholder engagement strategy.

Literature research will be performed, and online surveys/interviews will be conducted with prior projects experienced in implementing RRI in territorial R&I ecosystems, in order to build an agreed set of international practices, evidence-based and grounded in collaborative deliberations. This will be led by P3-QA, P2-TCD.

2) Ensure local-to-international multi-stakeholder collaboration and engagement within the QH framework: To maximise stakeholder engagement and facilitate mutual learning, OpenRRIHub will review previous and current EU (and beyond) projects which have successfully integrated the QH into efforts to develop an open and inclusive R&I ecosystem at the territorial level. These insights will feed into a strategic plan to mobilise the QH and build capacity to support development of RRI in territories, via practical support and ‘critical friend’ role. Furthermore, each OpenRRIHub will establish a local OpenRRIHubMB, with representatives from different QH societal stakeholders, which will be involved in all key processes and decisions of OpenRRIHubs. A mutual learning process across the participating territories will be developed and incentivized, and will include periodic structured sharing meetings with rotating chairs (maintaining gender balance and regional diversity in leadership of mutual learning). A project AB will also be established, where each AB member will be selected for a special relevant expertise, including coordination with research institutes, enterprises, industry, civil society organizations, local governments and wider society (including families); gender & diversity balance. The AB will both advise on key aspects of the project, safeguard the project objectives and evaluate the progress of the project. This will be led by P1-ULEI, P2-TCD, P4-IHS.

3) Establish multi-disciplinary Grand Challenge teams – OpenRRIHubs – to address and generate solutions to societal challenges through a mission-oriented strategy: OpenRRIHubs will work as knowledge brokers that facilitate processes to foster mutual learning among research, policy and practice, and will coordinate the cross-sectoral mission strategy between executive power offices, government departments and quadruple helices. The establishment of these teams within the respective institutional structure will be made taking into account the outputs from the Needs Assessment, context analysis and stakeholder mapping,, which will evaluate each institution’s current RRI maturity level, barriers and opportunities.

OpenRRIHubs will work with the respective governmental structures and local stakeholders to identify relevant key societal challenges, which will be broken down into concrete cross-sectoral missions. The Territorial Partners, in collaboration with local stakeholders, have made a preliminary assessment of relevant missions within the Horizon Europe Missions framework (Table 1.2). This will be led by P1-ULEI and P3-IHS.

Table 1.2: Relevant missions for Territorial Partners within the Horizon Europe Missions Framework

PARTNER	TERRITORIES	HORIZON EUROPE MISSIONS
P1-ULEI	Leiden, The Hague (NL): Local Government; Urban and Coastal	Cancer, climate-neutral and smart cities
P6-MFCR	Figueira de Castelo Rodrigo (PT): Local Government; Rural, Border-region	Adaptation to climate change including societal transformation, healthy oceans, seas coastal and inland waters, soil health and food
P7-AIRC	Azores (NL): Regional Government and Trans-European Network (involving: Angola, Brazil, Cape Verde, Ghana, Namibia, São Tomé e Príncipe, South Africa, United States of America) ¹⁰	Healthy oceans, seas coastal and inland waters
P8-FL	Aruba (AW): National Government	Cancer, adaptation to climate change including societal transformation, healthy oceans, seas coastal and inland waters, climate-neutral and smart cities, soil health and food

4) RRI institutional change training for territorial partners: OpenRRIHubs will build territorial capacity for RRI by developing tailored RRI action plans for each territory based on specific individual needs identified by the RRI Needs Assessment. Further, expert support will be offered alongside training on the specific RRI keys following development of training materials based on a review of training materials from EU (and beyond) previous and current RRI related projects that were designed to support institutional change pertaining to RRI. To build local capacity around RRI and leverage new partnerships, all Open RRI Hub partners and relevant local stakeholders will participate in these training workshops on effective tools for RRI localisation and implementation, community building, co-creation, and social entrepreneurship and innovation. The training workshops will also foster peer-to-peer learning, whereby participants can learn from each other's former experiences and previous projects. This will be led by P1-ULEI, P2-TCD and P3-QA.. Lead roles on RRI keys are: gender equality (Trinity College Dublin – also leading on this within OSHub project), societal/public engagement (Impact Hub), open access (Leiden University), governance (Impact Hub), ethics (Qualia Analytics), science education (Leiden University).

5) Implementation of OpenRRIHubs action plans – setting-up a mission-oriented strategy: The mission-oriented framework¹¹ explores five criteria for setting missions: be bold, inspirational and with wide societal relevance; set a clear direction that is targeted, measurable and time-bound; be ambitious but not unrealistic; be cross-disciplinary, cross-sectoral and cross-actor innovation; involve multiple, bottom-up solutions. Taking into account these criteria, the implementation of the mission-oriented strategy by OpenRRIHubs will comprise three key stages, as identified in the Missions Report, where community stakeholders and citizen becomes critical for missions:

- A) Co-creation of concrete missions that matter to society:** Identifying relevant societal challenges and transforming them into concrete measurable missions, that will be framed in a cross-sector manner, bringing in multiple actors and helping an economy become also differentiated, for each Territorial Partner location (For example, a cancer mission that only involves the health sector is not a mission in the way described above; it is if it also involves all the preventative areas, such as the nutrition sector and lifestyle areas¹²). As such, in each Territorial Partner location, missions will be defined via QH engagement sessions, facilitating dialogue and collective decision-making through collaborative and consensus driven processes.
- B) Co-implementation of missions:** Supporting the funding of cross-sectorial and multidisciplinary STEAM-based research and innovation pilot projects to address the identified missions, through an open call process in each Territorial Partner location, which will be selected by the OpenRRIHub teams and local OpenRRIHubMBs.
- C) Co-assessment of missions:** Strengthening the alignment between the processes and outcomes of the R&I projects and societal needs and expectations, by organizing periodic dialogue, monitoring and assessment sessions (every 6 months) with the selection committee and the project Advisory Board. Also, all the R&I processes,

10 <https://www.aircentre.org/network-levels/#nods>

11 Mazzucato, M. (2018) Missions: Mission-Oriented Research & Innovation in the European Union. European Commission. Available online at https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/communities/sites/jrccties/files/mazzucato_report_2018_0.pdf

12 https://www.ucl.ac.uk/bartlett/public-purpose/sites/public-purpose/files/190515_iipp_report_moiis_final_artwork_digital_export.pdf

results and outcomes will be open source, open hardware, open access, and under creative commons license attribution following closely the recommendations from the EU. This will be led by P1-ULEI.

6) Identification of common challenges across the different OpenRRIHubs with both local relevance and pan-European application and mutual learning: To achieve this, ‘lessons learned’ will be documented regularly throughout the project to establish institutional learning and share insights with other ongoing EU projects. Mutual learning meetings will be organized:

- At the network level, with OpenRRIHub partners, and AB members, to identify common challenges and opportunities, with local relevance and pan-European application, of the “border” communities where OpenRRIHubs will be established;
- At the local level, with local relevant stakeholders identified by the board, to co-create the approaches to addressing RRI-related needs and developing a more open, transparent and democratic R&I ecosystem.

This will be led by P2-TCD and P3-QA.

7) Assessment of the impact of OpenRRIHubs in the local communities: OpenRRIHub will implement ongoing monitoring and evaluation practices including participatory process evaluation and organisational impact evaluation in order to assess the progress of achieving stakeholder and citizen ownership and partnership development, as well as evaluating the impact of RRI institutional change and stakeholder engagement-oriented project interventions in the context of environmental decision-making. This will be built on impact measurement tools and methodologies developed by previously funded projects under this funding call, including TeRRIFICA. As part of developing these evaluation frameworks, a workshop will be convened with SwafS-14 project partners who have conducted impact assessment in prior years and past and ongoing projects, in order to take full advantage of this project’s placement at the end of the H2020 cycle. On-going impact assessment of the OpenRRIHubs will be provided and made publicly available to help provide citizens and future researchers with the tools and skills to make informed decisions and choices in this area. This will be led by P3-QA.

8) Facilitate knowledge circulation within the consortium and disseminate methodologies, resources and approaches to the wider public: All open source methodologies, resources, best practices and building plans will be made available to the wider public through the OpenRRIHub online platform. To ensure the legacy and reach of the project, OpenRRIHub will identify stakeholders in and beyond Europe that are likely to benefit from the insights and innovations of the project, and create material needed for these stakeholders to understand the results and innovations to be shared. This includes resources based on the material created for internal training for the participating institutions and wider RRI capacity building across territorial R&I ecosystems. Information products for dissemination through previously identified channels for insights, experiences and innovations derived from the mission phases and competition will also be created. Research produced by OpenRRIHub will be shared through peer-reviewed, open access publications, as well as publishing open data on the Zenodo platform founded by CERN, as well as active mutual learning processes to be established with other SwafS-14 projects. To empower territorial actors from across Europe (and beyond) to use OpenRRIHubs resources, each OpenRRIHub will organise continuing stakeholder and citizen engagement workshops aimed at the range of stakeholder types within the quadruple helix in order to widen the pool of interested stakeholders, leveraging the involvement and support of local players beyond the partners already engaged in the project. These will include provision of expert support, facilitation expertise and analysis guidance for at least one upstream stakeholder and citizen engagement workshop per study region and one downstream (focusing on dissemination of project results) stakeholder and citizen engagement workshop per study region. Also, a final OpenRRIHub Summit will bring together all partners and key stakeholders to consolidate the outcomes of the project, share best practices and discuss the sustainability and legacy of OpenRRIHubs. This will be led by P5-SN.

9) Building a legacy and sustainability plan for the future: A legacy and sustainability plan for the project will be developed, ensuring that RRI is incorporated in the partner local institutions’ and governments’ vision and programme. Alongside the sustainability measures which will be included in the individual territory action plans, this legacy plan will unfold along 2 action lines: to analyse from a financially sustainable perspective the material, resources and knowledge developed during the project and to offer the consortium the tools to convert the OpenRRIHubs into a self-sustaining social enterprise. Additionally, as this is the final call for SwafS-14, all insights, techniques, methodologies and outcomes developed by the project will be synthesised and into carefully structured toolkit content designed to be freely available through Creative Commons licensing, based on the knowledge developed through the project. This toolkit will create a sustainable capacity-building tool that provides a SwafS14-wide legacy synthesising learning from across all SwafS14 projects for the benefit of territorial researchers, innovators, students and policy-makers. It will be designed with several entry points and learning pathways for heterogeneous audiences with diverse interests and professional needs, as well as cultural backgrounds and language requirements. As with other aspects of the project, we will orient this work towards the Horizon Europe mainstreaming of RRI, with a particular contribution at the level of regional R&I ecosystems. This will be led by P8-FL.

1.3.2. National or international research and innovation activities which are linked with the project

Table 1.3: National or international research and innovation activities which are linked with the project

RESEARCH & INNOVATION ACTIVITIES	OUTPUTS WHICH WILL FEED INTO OPENRRIHUBS
<p>H2020 SwafS-14 TeRRIFICA</p>	<p>QA is leading on monitoring and evaluation and risk management and reporting for TeRRIFICA. The co-creation approach and tools developed within TeRRIFICA can be adapted and re-used in OpenRRIHubs. Moreover, the evaluation instruments and processes can largely be re-used in OpenRRIHubs, providing a strong link between OpenRRIHubs and TeRRIFICA, opportunities for benchmarking and mutual learning between the projects. Partners involved: P3-QA</p>
<p>H2020 SwafS-14 RRING</p>	<p>QA has played a key role in the methodological aspects of the RRING project, focusing on different levels of survey measurement of RRI policies and practices on a global level. As part of its contribution to RRING, QA experts have been critical to the development and piloting of the Indicators Framework for the UNESCO Recommendation on Science and Scientific Researchers, which is being piloted during the RRING project in Ireland and Lithuania, and will then be offered as a global solution for measuring the health of R&I ecosystems. The methodological innovations in impact measurement and indicators for evaluating R&I ecosystems will be applied at the territorial level in this project. Partners involved: P3-QA</p>
<p>H2020 GRRIP</p>	<p>GRRIP's focus on implementing and evaluating institutional changes associated with RRI action plans directly relates to the current project. QA's evaluation work on indicators of RRI-related institutional changes in GRRIP enables it to bring over lessons both in terms of evaluation approaches and in findings about best practice in territorial RRI action plan implementation across a diverse range of settings. Partners involved: P3-QA</p>
<p>H2020 Swafs-01 OSHub</p>	<p>OSHub Network – a network of Open Schooling Hubs – contributes to the development, innovation and well-being of underserved communities close to geographical and social borders, by creating community hubs for open collaboration, where schools and communities address local relevant challenges, based on multi-stakeholder collaboration, and have access to resources and tools to develop Inquiry-Based STEAM Education, citizen-science and makercentred projects. Partners involved: P1-ULEI (Project coordinator), P2-TCD, P3-IHS, P6-MFCR</p>
<p>FP7 RRI Tools</p>	<p>OpenRRIHub partners have contributed to the project toolkit and have attended “Train The Trainer” sessions, and will act as RRI Tools trainers for partners. The activities and resources developed by the project will be uploaded to the RRI Tools Toolkit, with OpenRRIHubs members becoming part of the RRI Tools community of practice. Partners involved: P2-TCD.</p>
<p>H2020 PERFORM</p>	<p>QA experts' work on the enabling role of social media in RRI-themed science education during the PERFORM project offers valuable insights for both communication and RRI innovation aspects of the current project. Partners involved: P3-QA</p>
<p>H2020 EU-Citizen.Science</p>	<p>The EU-Citizen platform will develop a mutual learning space where different tools, best practice examples and relevant scientific outcomes are collected, curated, and made accessible to different stakeholders, ranging from interested citizens and media over scientific institutions up to politicians and donor organisations. Partner involved: P1-ULEI, P2-TCD & P6-MFCR</p>
<p>H2020 Big Picnic</p>	<p>The work in BigPicnic on co-creation methods and how to upskill partners inexperienced in the use of co-creation will be a key asset to feed into the current project. QA was the evaluation lead on this project, meaning that it is in a particularly good position to introduce lessons learned from BigPicnic's largely successful efforts to develop capacity for co-creation. Partners involved: P3-QA</p>
<p>H2020 SwafS-19 QUEST</p>	<p>QUEST is a H2020 project focused on defining measures and supports for quality in science communication. The project is developing tools, recommendations, and guidelines for communicators and practitioners working in the fields of journalism, social media, and museums. Partners involved: P2-TCD.</p>

H2020 HYPATIA	HYPATIA gathers different societal actors to bring more teenagers, especially girls, into STEM careers. The project created a toolkit of gender-inclusive activities, and guidelines in gender – sensitivity for teachers and educators of young people. These tools will inform the creation of gender-equity guidelines. Partner involved: P2-TCD.
FP7 STUDIOLAB	Studiolab was a 3-year Europe-wide initiative that aimed to merge the studio with the research lab. Funded by EC FP7 and led by Science Gallery Dublin, Studiolab created a European network that provided a platform for creative projects that bridge divisions between science, art and design. Science Gallery Dublin developed three exhibitions as part of the Studiolab project: SURFACE TENSION (2011), HACK THE CITY (2012) and GROW YOUR OWN (2014). Partner involved: P2-TCD
H2020 Sparks	SPARKS was a Horizon 2020-funded 3 year project led by Ecsite. The partnership consisted of 33 organisations from 29 European countries. The central activity was a travelling interactive exhibition around the topic of health, which visited each country throughout the lifetime of the project. Each partner country worked with local promising RRI practices in the area of health, and developed a local case study to be part of the exhibition. Alongside the exhibition were a number of public engagement activities: science cafés, hackathons and creative workshops, offering the public the opportunity to identify priority research questions and co-design scientific solutions along with experts from research and industry. Partner involved: P2-TCD
FP7 BENISI	BENISI is a FP7 EU funded project to support the scaling of social innovation. The toolkit that was produced as a deliverable will be used to evaluate how OpenRRIHub can become financially sustainable beyond the project at local level and as a European network. Partner involved: P4-IHS.
Voices	VOICES (Views, Opinions and Ideas of Citizens in Europe on Science) has run a Europe-wide public consultation initiative, providing valuable know-how on methodological and procedural aspects for the structural employment of citizens participation in defining the European research agenda in the framework of Responsible Research and Innovation.
OpenCare	OPENCARE project brings a diverse community together – citizens with expert knowledge on health care, social care, service design, digital fabrication, collective intelligence and public policy evaluation to design, prototype and evaluate care services by communities, for communities.
H2020 DITOS	DITOs aims to increase public participation in scientific research and innovation across Europe. DITOs builds the institutional and policy foundations for sustained deep public engagement in science and technology in Europe that enables people to contribute at a level of participation suitable for them.

1.3.3. Methodology

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)

We understand that SwafS and RRI are at a key pivot point as the Horizon 2020 funding programme ends. The new direction of further ‘mainstreaming’ RRI into the main research and innovation funding stream for Horizon Europe brings new opportunities and challenges. This project aims to support the effort to marshal the resources from SwafS work on territorial RRI implementation within H2020 and ensure that there is long-term infrastructure and resources available to Horizon Europe to support the integration of RRI in its core work. RRI offers a pathway forward for stakeholders to share responsibility for innovation and development within R&I ecosystems, taking account of societal needs and defining socially desirable research goals and technologies. By actively involving societal actors in the project structure, OpenRRIHub can demonstrate the model that RRI encapsulates, and contribute to the research and innovation process in action.

Mission-oriented approach

The concept of mission-oriented innovation policies is at the centre of Horizon Europe. Mission-oriented policies can be defined as systemic public policies that draw on frontier knowledge to attain specific goals. While the archetypical

historical mission is NASA putting a man on the Moon, contemporary missions aim to address broader challenges that require long-term commitment to the development of challenges that are as much social as technological¹³. The Mission-oriented approach is at the core of the OpenRRIHUB project and will be tested not only in terms of concept, through the design of Mission Roadmaps, with measurable and time-bound targets, but also by proposing to do it through the establishment of innovative cross-sectoral structures inside governmental institutions – OpenRRIHubs, promoting bottom-up R&I projects and the engagements of citizens from mission creation, to implementation and assessment.

Continuous evaluation based on QH engagement and mutual learning process

From an early stage, the formative and embedded evaluation dimension of the project will feed into the ongoing shaping and evolution of the areas of focus and means of implementing the action. Barriers to progress and opportunities for gaining extra impact will be assessed in advance through the formative evaluation. Then, each aspect of the project will be monitored for its effectiveness. Monitoring, particularly with digital evaluation tools that enable real time data analysis, will inform the OpenRRIHUB partners' strategies for conducting their work. The evaluation framework for the project will also ensure that the participatory approaches adopted by the project are validated or adjusted as needed based on incoming evaluation findings. This evidence-based approach – rooted in continuous monitoring – will enable us to maximise impact. Moreover, the generalisability of both previously proposed best practice and any new innovations trialled by OpenRRIHUB will be rigorously assessed to ensure that only the proven best practice and associated principles are enshrined in the project resources that are made available for use in Horizon Europe and beyond. In this way, the project will stand on the shoulders of giants (integrating previous projects' best practice) while ensuring that the guidelines we communicate onward are tried and tested in a fresh set of regions.

Figure 1.3: OpenRRIHubs approach and mutual learning process to ensure shared development across participating territories throughout the phases of project Implementation

Upstream public engagement and participation to define agenda

Aligning the best practice developed by the TeRRIFICA (SwafS-14) project and re-using the open source software for this purpose developed in that project, we will employ a participatory approach to prioritisation and targeting of our work. This includes open data collection processes using the 'crowd mapping' platform developed within TeRRIFICA to identify priorities valued by local citizens relating to research and innovation. QH stakeholders will participate in the development of implementation plans for the OpenRRIHubs, based around the identification of regional needs and priorities.

Applying Quadruple Helix framework implementing open and inclusive approaches

A crucial underpinning of the development of the OpenRRIHubs is an ongoing focus on implementing evidence-based, effective stakeholder engagement and mutual learning processes tailored to the quadruple helices: government, industry, academia and civil society in each participating territory, to ensure effective participation in the process and local 'ownership' of the project. The QH framework is essential to an effective R&I ecosystem in the sense that territorial partners must mobilise their local stakeholders to address the identified mission and local challenges. OpenRRIHubs will provide the open resources, skills and knowledge to facilitate local stakeholder engagement and mutual learning processes and activities, and ensure local governments' capacity for collaboration with other societal actors is as extensive and inclusive as possible.

Integrating Design Thinking

Design Thinking^{14, 15}, is a problem-solving approach to learning that involves human-centred design in tackling real-world problems, through research, empathy, creativity, prototyping and reiteration. OpenRRIHub will use the methodologies of Design Thinking in co-creation and participatory workshops and events with OpenRRIHub partners, the AB, and other relevant local stakeholders, to identify common relevant challenges across the different OpenRRIHubs and to co-create the OpenRRIHub – and local government-driven content and programme. The project will take a participatory approach in general, drawing on the extensive expertise of partners in co-creation and citizen science, including experience with evaluation of the effectiveness of participatory approaches by QA in prior SwafS projects with major co-creation dimensions such as Big-Picnic, TeRRIFICA and GRRIP.

Maintaining Open Standards

OpenRRIHub will be fully based on Open Standards, processes, protocols or resources made available to the general public, and developed and maintained via a collaborative and consensus driven process¹⁶. All the OpenRRIHub resources will be open source, open access and under a Creative Commons License, following closely the recommendations from the EU. OpenRRIHub will work with open hardware and open software wherever possible and scientific publications will be submitted to Open Access journals. PI-ULEI has several years of experience developing Open Education Resources¹⁷, developing a community of practice for Open Standards in STEAM¹⁸ and using Open Standards to establish small scale science hubs, the Open Science Hub¹⁹.

1.3.4. OpenRRIHub Gender Equality Dimension

The Treaty of the European Union aims to eliminate gender inequality and promote equal opportunities for women. In accordance with the Treaty of Amsterdam (1997) and other EU policy reports (EUR 2002/2), as well as the UN Global Goals, establishing equality between men and women is a priority. OpenRRIHub is committed to incorporating the principles of gender equality (while also addressing intersectional factors) mainstreaming throughout the entire project, giving equal consideration to the different life patterns, needs and interests of male and female participants and project members. Here, we will be drawing on the European Framework for Researchers Careers²⁰ and the Code and Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers²¹ to highlight the importance of inclusive policies and norms. All OpenRRIHub events and activities will be inclusive and equitable for all genders and orientations and are developed and executed according to gender equity recommendations (e.g., using Toolkit from H2020 Hypatia, and examples provided by the IASC Gender Handbook²²). Gender equity guidelines will be provided to all OpenRRIHub partners, with supporting training, mentoring and feedback provided by specialists within the consortium. Gender balance will be ensured in OpenRRIHub activities, and gender equality will be rigorously evaluated both at the level of objective statistics and in terms of partner perceptions of empowerment, inclusion, etc. In addition, a dedicated member of the AB will be assigned to monitor the gender dimension of OpenRRIHub. There is a great deal of detail-oriented work involved in ensuring gender equality within our project. A key focus will be to address barriers to recruitment, retention and effective career progression for women working at partner institutions. We will collaboratively analyse the status of women in participating organisations at the outset of the project, and identify solutions that can overcome barriers identified in a way that is sensitive to local cultural constraints, barriers and opportunities to progress on gender equality and distinctive challenges faced within different R&I ecosystems. We will target this and other aspects of gender equality within the consortium (and aim to radiate out to regional R&I ecosystems).

1.3.5. Track record implementing RRI processes by the OpenRRIHub partners

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) is a core policy principle for OpenRRIHub. All the partners have experience with societal aspects of research, namely: public engagement, research integrity and ethics and with a focus on aligning

14 Wagner, T., Compton, R.A., 2012. Creating innovators: the making of young people who will change the world.

15 Crichton, S. & Carter, D. (2015). Taking Making Into the Schools: An Immersive Professional Development Approach. In M. Niess & H. Gillow Wiles (Eds.). Handbook of Research on Teacher Education in the Digital Age. IGI Global.

16 Rosen, L. (2009) "Defining Open Standards", pp. 2-4.

17 Leiden University received the SPORE Award from Science Magazine for the openness of its educational resources: <http://www.unawe.org/press/UNAW1103/>
<http://www.open.org.pt/>

18 <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/824581>

20 http://ec.europa.eu/euraxess/pdf/research_policies/Towards_a_European_Framework_for_Research_Careers_final.pdf

21 http://ec.europa.eu/euraxess/pdf/brochure_rights/am509774CEE_EN_E4.pdf

22 www.humanitarianresponse.info/system/files/documents/files/Gender%20Handbook.pdf

23 <https://www.universiteitleiden.nl/en/dossiers/diversity/diversity-office-and-diversity-team>

24 <https://www.universiteitleiden.nl/en/news/2019/09/four-years-of-womens-network-at-the-faculty-of-science>

research and innovation processes and outcomes to the values and needs of the greater society. Table 1.4 provides an overview of consortium experience in implementing RRI processes.

Table 1.4: Consortium experience in implementing RRI processes

PARTNER	ROLE	EXPERIENCE IN IMPLEMENTING RRI PROCESSES
ULEI	RRI expert & Territorial Partner	ULEI has experience with the six main dimensions of RRI, namely research engagement with society through the Department of Science Communication & Society, gender equality through the Leiden Uni Diversity & Inclusion Office ²³ and RISE network ²⁴ , open science through Leiden Open Science Community, science education through several Swafs projects such as the Open Science Hub, and ethics and governance in Research and Innovation with close R&I partnerships in Leiden and the Hague (Leiden Center for Innovation and Entrepreneurship and Center for Innovation The Hague).
TCD	RRI expert	TCD has had a central role in the formation of European policy regarding RRI since 2014 due to its participation in the RRI-TOOLS project — an FP7 SiS project to define RRI for future European projects as well as producing training and dissemination toolkits for research, civil society, industry, and education. Since then, TCD — especially the Science & Society Research Group encompassing the School of Education and Science Gallery Dublin — has participated in 15 European projects relating to the core pillars of RRI: Science Education, Gender, Public Engagement, Ethics, and Open Access. TCD can provide a unique test case in science education by combining both standard academic courses with a cultural space for informal learning — Science Gallery Dublin. In particular, Science Gallery offers an art-science programme for young adults (15-18 years of age). This programme is for 20 participants at a time who take part in a week-long course that highlights the rich network of interconnections between science, the arts, culture, design, business, and innovation. There are on-average 10 iterations of this programme offered each year and priority places are given to students from disadvantaged schools. As the programme is built on the core tenets of RRI it would be an invaluable addition to the OpenRRIHubs project.
IHS	RRI expert	IHS experience related with RRI focuses on services related to the access to Finance and non-financial services for regional SMEs: +1000 requests for microloans; +100 Business Plans evaluated; +50 regional SMEs financed within the framework of microfinance projects: Jeremie Sicilia, Microcredito Siciliano and Banca Popolare Etica microloans. More broadly, RRI is performed by IHS on the design, planning and delivery of high quality training (Project Management for Social Innovation) and the delivery of a vast range of events to promote active citizenship and participatory governance, together with social entrepreneurship (Startup Weekend – ChangeMakers; A Brighter Future for Europe: Innovation, Integration and the Migrant Crisis), to map entrepreneurial ecosystem and connect private and public sector (Startup Europe Week Siracusa; EIT Food Challenge Lab 2019).
QA	RRI expert	QA's experience in implementing RRI processes is extensive, both within and outside EU projects. Within EU projects, QA experience includes key roles in integrating upstream stakeholder engagement within scientific institutions as part of EU-Zoos-XXI (FP7 CSA), supporting the introduction of evidence-based science education and outreach practices within the MARCH (H2020 SwafS CSA) project, advising on public and stakeholder engagement processes and wider RRI training in the BigPicnic project (H2020 SwafS CSA), enabling effective integration of RRI into science education through social media-based engagement in PERFORM (H2020 SwafS RIA), providing expertise on ethics, multistakeholder engagement and the inclusion of gender equality and inclusive practices in survey research for the RRING (H2020 SwafS RIA) project, supporting refinement of SMART objectives and stakeholder engagement skills, as well as robust ongoing evaluation for the TeRRIFICA (H2020 SwafS-14 CSA) project, delivering evaluation expertise for measuring indicators of RRI institutional changes in GRRIP (CSA), providing external expertise to re-design ethics and open data management process throughout Project O's consortium (H2020 IA) and delivering RRI impact evaluation expertise and support in MUSICA (H2020 RIA). Qualia has been critical to the development and piloting of the Indicators Framework for the UNESCO Recommendation on Science and Scientific Researchers, a global policy instrument that promotes RRI principles through a treaty ratified by 195 UN Member-States. Each of these projects have required RRI expertise that can be translated into practical action, mentoring and support for territorial, government, RFOs and RPOs to develop improved practices.

SN	RRI expert	<p>Science Now was an initiator and delivery partner of an innovative science & arts residency programme that was run in fall 2019 in Poland through a grant by the Ministry of Culture for “Supporting Growth of the Creative Industries”. The programme coalesced over 24 creators, designers and makers to address four societal themes: climate emergency, cities of sounds, spaceship Earth and AI for good. The programme involved a diverse range of mentors and experts: scientists, strategic designers, futurists and artists – ranging from cross-European institutions such as Ars Electronica, Copenhagen Institute for Interaction Design and European Space Agency, as well as over 15 Polish cultural and scientific institutions. The programme was heavily informed on and relied on principles of the Responsible Research & Innovation framework.</p>
MFCR	Territorial partner	<p>In 2017, the MFCR, located in a rural area in the northeast border between Portugal and Spain, started a social innovation project – entitled Plataforma de Ciência Aberta (Open Science Hub – Portugal) – aimed at bringing together science, technology and innovation with the daily-life of local communities, through open schooling, citizen science and social innovation. The MFCR has experience with RRI, namely with the RRI keys Science Education and Public Engagement, which have been strengthened by the participation in two H2020 projects that are currently running: the OSHub and the EU-Citizen.Science project.</p>
AIRC	Territorial partner	<p>The AIR Centre is an internationally networked organization, oriented to foster job creation and knowledge-driven sustainable economic development in Atlantic regions. It addresses and integrates space, climate, earth, ocean, energy and data sciences and promotes south-north/north-south cooperation in alignment with national/regional priorities and global challenges such as the UN 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, the Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021-2030), the Paris Agreement and the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction. The AIR Centre is all about advancing science and technology on a responsible and transformative scale in the Atlantic region. It builds on and expands what individual organizations can do and it advances selected scientific and technological domains and their constellations of actors towards shared targets. This complexity comes from the AIR Centre’s unique multidimensional mission-oriented, demand-driven, problem-solving approach, which integrates various sciences (space, ocean, earth, climate, energy, and data sciences), includes different stakeholders (government, academia, industry, and civil society), encompasses diverse geographies, cultures and technology readiness levels (American, African and European countries), and fully accommodates both local priorities and global challenges.</p>
FL	Territorial partner	<p>FL was established in 2018 with the purpose to aid in the design, development and implementation of a national innovation strategy for Aruba. FL has received the mandate to implement the Government of Aruba’s centred national innovation plan, named Aruba Innova 2030. Futura serves as Aruba’s innovation lab and national think-tank on innovation. FL, a first of its kind innovation lab in the Caribbean, collaborates with local and international innovators on pioneering innovation initiatives to stimulate the knowledge and innovation capacity of the Aruban society.</p>

2. Impact

2.1. Expected impacts

Our targeted impacts in OpenRRIHub are specific, measurable, accepted, realistic and time-bound, with an emphasis on participatory, upstream engagement approaches that involve the quadruple helix to ensure the effectiveness of our planned action as it seeks to catalyse change in regional R&I ecosystems. The evaluation will track whether the project is reaching target audiences, as well as the different types of stakeholders in the participating regions. It will also evaluate RRI-related institutional changes in partner institutions.

The evidence-based approach in the project will enhance impact by ensuring that any gaps between the expected impacts and ongoing empirical findings are immediately flagged for adaptation of the approach. The territorial activities will be developed and applied along the KPIs in a recursive structure to ensure effectiveness, drawing upon indicators developed and

refined in TeRRIFICA and other Swafs projects (including projects involving our evaluation WP lead, such as RRI-Tools, RRING, GRRIP and PERFORM) and aligned with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals.

The following sections describe the specific actions through which OpenRRIHubs answers the specific expected impacts for OpenRRIHubs target audiences on the short, medium and long term, and how they relate to the Recommendation from the “Governing Missions in the European Union” Report²⁵. Each section also estimates the impact of OpenRRIHubs actions for each target group. In particular, OpenRRIHub will contribute to the four impacts described in the Work Programme.

2.1.1. Short term impact: 0–3 years

Consortia are expected to elaborate and implement a more open, transparent and democratic R&I System in their defined territories

Governments and administration

Actions: The OpenRRIHub network will establish Grand Challenge knowledge brokers teams – OpenRRIHubs – in governmental structures to tackle relevant societal challenges. They will utilise a Mission-oriented approach, operating across sectors, drawing policy expertise from across government departments and bringing technical know-how and expertise from a broad R&I infrastructure formed by other members of the QH (Rec. 6²⁶).

The Territorial Partners consist of three governmental institutions – local (P6-MFCR), regional (P7-AIRC) and national (P8-FL) – and a university with formal links to local municipalities (P1-ULEI). As such the establishment of the OpenRRIHubs will take place within the institutional structure of these institutions, and will coordinate the cross-sectoral mission strategy between executive power offices, government departments and quadruple helices. In order for the establishment of the OpenRRIHubs in their host institutions to be tailored and effective, leading to sustainable institutional and more open, transparent and democratic processes, each Territorial Partner will go through the following methodological framework led by the respective RRI Expert Partners:

- RRI Institutional Change Assessment, to evaluate each institution’s current RRI maturity level, barriers and opportunities (WP2, led by P3-QA);
- Establishment of the OpenRRIHub teams within the respective institutions and in relation to the community partners, and establishment of the respective Structures, Strategies and Protocols, including: defining institutional organisational chart, with clear network flow, division of responsibilities and ownership; establishing local OpenRRIHub Management Boards (local OpenRRIHubMB; with representatives from different QH societal stakeholders), which will be involved in all key processes and decisions of OpenRRIHubs; defining open and transparent internal communication system, both internal (inside the host institution) and external (with community partners; WP3, led by P4-IHS);
- Training of OpenRRIHub teams (and relevant community stakeholders) on the RRI Keys – Gender equality, Societal/public engagement, Open access, Governance, Ethics and Science education – to develop capacity in OpenRRIHub teams establishment (WP2, led by P3-QA);
- Creation and implementation of RRI Action Plans for each Territorial Partner location, based on identified best practices. These Action Plans will be grounded on three key stages, as identified in the Missions Report²⁷: 1) How to involve community stakeholders and citizens in the definition and selection of concrete missions that matter to society; 2) How community stakeholders and citizens participate in the implementation of missions; 3) How community stakeholders and citizens will be involved in the assessment (evaluation, review and monitoring process) of missions (WP4, led by P1-ULEI);
- Training of OpenRRIHub teams on stakeholder engagement to ensure effective, open, transparent and democratic participation of the QA and citizens during the implementation of the RRI Action Plans (WP5, led by P2-TCD);
- Mutual learning visits and calls between the territorial partners (WP5, led by P2-TCD).

Impact Estimators:

- 4 RRI institutional change evaluation framework & impact evaluation reports (1 per Territorial Partner)
- 4 OpenRRIHubs Structures, Strategies and Protocols (1 per Territorial Partner)

25 https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/research_and_innovation/contact/documents/ec_rtd_mazzucato-report-issue2_072019.pdf

26 Recommendation 6: The implementation of missions will benefit from breaking down silos by coordinating actions between departments, with a clear division of responsibilities and ownership. To achieve maximum impact, it is key that this is coordinated by the highest offices of the executive power

27 Mazzucato, M. (2018) Missions: Mission-Oriented Research & Innovation in the European Union. European Commission. Available online at https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/communities/sites/jrccties/files/mazzucato_report_2018_0.pdf

- 4 RRI Action Plans - Mission-oriented strategy Toolkit (1 per Territorial Partner)
- 4 Mission-Oriented Policy Plans (1 per Territorial Partner)
- 4 Training Workshops on Stakeholder Engagement (1 per Territorial Partner)
- 5 mutual learning visits per partner
- Each OpenRRIHub will collect data about RRI institutional change in the Territorial Partner Institutions according to the guidelines provided by WP2: Monitoring, Evaluation and Reflective Practices

Academia, Industry and Civil Society

Actions: Academia, Industry and Civil Society representatives will be part of the local OpenRRIHubMBs, and as such will be involved in all key processes and decisions of OpenRRIHubs. In addition, they will also integrate the project AB where each member will be selected for a special relevant expertise, including coordination with research institutes, enterprises, industry, civil society organizations, local governments and wider society (including families); gender & diversity balance. Moreover, academia, industry and civil society will be active players throughout the entire mission process (1.3.1 Overall Concept) – where not only their participation will be fundamental, but, also, most importantly, joint and collaborative work, with concrete goals and outcomes, including mission definition, project selection and evaluation and funding allocation (Rec. 7²⁸). In particular:

- Co-creation of missions, through engagement and collective decision-making sessions – with policy makers, professionals from enterprises, research institutes, civil society organizations and citizens, in each Territorial Partner location – , where relevant societal challenges will be identified and transformed into concrete measurable missions.
- Co-implementation of missions, through an open call process, where any QH institution will be able to submit their mission-oriented R&I proposals. Proposals will be required to be grounded in a cross-sector manner, to bring in multiple actors and to promote economy to become differentiated. Citizen science and social innovation projects will be actively encouraged (Rec. 3²⁹). Proposals will be selected by the OpenRRIHubs and the local OpenRRIHubMBs.
- Co-assessment of missions, through periodic monitoring and assessment sessions (every 6 months) with the local OpenRRIHubMB and the project Advisory Board, and creation of open and citizen-oriented bi-directional communication strategy, with sharing of all the R&I processes, results and outcomes, for citizens to understand the value of R&I actions and the tangible impact on their lives (Rec. 5³⁰), as well as enabling citizens' experiences and observations to monitor progress towards mission objectives (Rec. 4³¹).

OpenRRIHubs will also impact the following

Academia

Mission-oriented approaches and RRI provide an excellent opportunity to better align R&I and its outcomes with the values, needs and expectations of society, helping, not only, to redefine the role of researchers in society and the interactions between science and society, but also strengthening research projects by emphasizing openness, transparency, diversity, inclusiveness and adaptation to changes. In addition, by working in a cross-sectorial manner and in collaboration with other stakeholders, besides opening up the door for more diverse and integrative research questions, it might also bring more diverse sources of funding.

Industry

In the case of Industry, the engagement in Mission-oriented approaches and RRI, will bring a range of possibilities and impacts, such as co-creating innovations together with the people affected by them, co-designing whole systems in a cross-sectorial way (e.g. health care, food system, mobility) instead of focusing on individual technologies or products, developing new technologies, products, services and business models that are socially acceptable and desirable.

28 Recommendation 7: The mission governance should be empowered with a high-level structure including leaders from academia, business and citizen groups. These will exert leadership through advice on funding allocation, project selection and evaluation, and experimentation with new work modalities

29 Recommendation 3: Citizen scientists and innovators can have clear added value and complement the implementation of missions. Their participation should be actively encouraged.

30 Recommendation 5: citizen-oriented communication & dissemination activities should be ensured throughout the entire life cycle of missions, in order for citizens around Europe to understand the value of R&I actions and the tangible impact on their lives.

31 Recommendation 4: Missions should enable the use of citizens' experiences and observations to monitor progress towards mission objectives.

Civil Society

Civil society and citizens are the key to avoid unrealistic expectations and the decoupling between policy, science and society. As mentioned before, civil society will be an active player throughout the entire mission process, through co-creation, engagement and collective decision-making sessions, ensuring that all citizens, namely citizen movements, civil society organizations, workers, and under-represented groups, have a voice in the design, development and assessment of the mission proposals (Rec. 1³²), playing a meaningful role in agenda setting processes and in the democratisation of R&I. This becomes particularly relevant in this project, considering that OpenRRIHubs will be created in communities that traditionally do not engage with R&I or do not bring RRI dimensions into the R&I processes due to various barriers (geographical location, socio-economic status, or minority ethnic group background).

The establishment of an open and citizen-oriented bi-directional communication plan in each Territorial Plan will also be pivotal for citizens to understand the value and impact of R&I in their daily lives, as well as enabling them to actively monitor the progress of the R&I projects.

Impact Estimators:

- At least, 8 co-creation sessions for mission definition (2 per Territorial Partner)
- 4 concrete Missions and 4 Mission RoadMap (1 per Territorial Partner)
- At least, 8 Mission-oriented R&I projects selected and developed, with respective impact assessment reports (at least, 2 per Territorial Partner)
- 8 monitoring and assessment sessions (2 per Territorial Partner)
- 4 open and citizen-oriented bi-directional communication plans to share R&I processes (1 per Territorial Partner)
- 20 partnerships with Universities and Research Institutes (5 per Territorial Partner)
- 20 partnerships with Industry (5 per Territorial Partner)
- 20 partnerships with Civil Society Organizations (5 per Territorial Partner)
- Each OpenRRIHub will collect data about RRI institutional change in OpenRRIHub QH Partners according to the guidelines provided by WP2: Monitoring, Evaluation and Reflective Practices

2.1.2. Short term impact: 0–3 years & Medium term impact: 3–5 years

Consortia are expected to evaluate their activities and provide evidence of societal, democratic, environmental, economic and scientific impacts.

Governments and administration (internally and in relation to stakeholders)

Our approach and strategy for evaluating impacts in these areas is detailed in WP2 – Monitoring, Evaluation and Reflective Practice, and will be led by expert evaluation partner P3-QA. This approach synthesises best practice from previous H2020 SwafS projects and lays the groundwork for effectively engaging and mobilizing territorial stakeholders to foster long-term integration of RRI principles of open and inclusive innovation into R & I ecosystems by assessing current RRI capacity against key RRI institutional change indicators, and facilitating evidence-based decision-making about how best to integrate RRI within participating territories.

This will be underpinned by effective ongoing evaluation and monitoring in a continuous cycle of improvement and measurement (Figure 1.3). Indeed, OpenRRIHub's strive for impact will be based on an iterative approach, i.e. it enables all other work packages, beneficiaries and stakeholders, to reflect the individual progress and contributions in a much wider context of RRI institutional change, participatory decision-making processes, and communication activities, in any of the 4 territories. This will foster a process in which the project can continuously reflect and adapt its approaches in loops. Evaluation becomes more than a measure of change: it becomes a source of ideation and optimisation. The impact of the project will be primarily measured by the extent to which it will have generated systemic transformation. Key performance indicators along the MoRRI indicators (Table 2.1) will be assessed e.g. to which degree of formalized RRI structures / mechanisms at the territorial and institutional level in the context of environmental decision-making exist. Further, RRI practices of participating partners and associated organisations will be evaluated and enhanced to ensure a reflective approach.

Impact estimators: RRI institutional change evaluation framework based on synthesis of best practice in application of MoRRI indicators at the territorial and institutional level; Lessons learned report from citizen and engagement collaborative workshops and related work and RRI institutional change impact evaluation report.

Quadruple Helix: Government, Academia, Civil Society, Industry

As shown in Figure 1.1, a mission-oriented approach starts by breaking down a broad challenge (such as tackling climate change) into a concrete mission (for example, a carbon-neutral city), which carries inherent success metrics, i.e. missions must be framed as time-bound and to have measurable targets that are clear in terms of whether they are achieved or not. In addition, the success of the mission-oriented approach relies on a long-term outlook, and the cross-sectoral, bottom-up development of solutions.

As such, a concrete and specific output of the co-creation sessions to define the mission-oriented strategy in each Territorial Partner location will be a RoadMap which includes:

- the Grand Challenge that will be tackled
- a concrete Mission, time-bound and with measurable targets
- the sectors that will be involved given the defined objectives (e.g. health, culture, ICT)

In Figure 2.1, we provide an example of a Mission Roadmap from the report “A Mission-Oriented Industrial Strategy”³³.

Figure 2.1: Clean Growth Mission Roadmap³⁴

33 https://www.ucl.ac.uk/bartlett/public-purpose/sites/public-purpose/files/190515_iipp_report_moiis_final_artwork_digital_export.pdf
 34 https://www.ucl.ac.uk/bartlett/public-purpose/sites/public-purpose/files/190515_iipp_report_moiis_final_artwork_digital_export.pdf

These Mission Roadmaps will work as the base for the Mission-oriented R&I projects Open Call. In each Territorial Partner location, the OpenRRIHubs together with the local OpenRRIHubMB, will define the Mission-oriented R&I projects Guidelines, which will establish a set of specific evaluation and assessment criteria. The R&I projects will be required to tackle the mission with measurable indicators, to be cross-sector and to bring in multiple actors – to be undertaken by businesses, governments, universities, civil society organizations. Proposals will be selected by the OpenRRIHubs and local OpenRRIHubMBs. The selected R&I projects will undergo periodic monitoring and assessment that will be performed together with the local OpenRRIHubMBs and project AB.

Impact Estimators:

- 4 concrete Missions and 4 Mission RoadMap (1 per Territorial Partner)
- At least, 8 Mission-oriented R&I projects selected and developed, with respective impact assessment reports (at least, 2 per Territorial Partner)
- 20 partnerships with Universities and Research Institutes (5 per Territorial Partner)
- 20 partnerships with Industry (5 per Territorial Partner)
- 20 partnerships with Civil Society Organizations (5 per Territorial Partner)

2.1.3. Long-term impact: 5 – 10 years

Involvement in the project should have a measurable transformative and opening effect on organisations involved, which should be sustainable beyond the lifetime of funding

Through deep and continued stakeholder engagement, awareness of the drivers, expectations and challenges limiting each QH stakeholders' participation in the change processes will be generated and incorporated into project planning and QH engagement strategies. This will be crucial for ensuring ongoing engagement in RRI for the territorial partners beyond the lifetime of funding. The RRI action plans which will be developed will include strategies to implement institutional changes which sustainably engage the QH and ensure the territorial partners follow more open and inclusive practices in the policy development process on a long-term basis. Further, through WP7, strategies to disseminate resources beyond the lifetime of the project and knowledge outcomes within established networks will be developed (tasks 7.1, 7.2), alongside a strategy to integrate knowledge outcomes in relevant programmes run by the partners on a permanent basis in order to enhance economic sustainability of the project.

In terms of ensuring the sustainability of each OpenRRIHub, tailored business models including market study and segmentation, business plan, social impact, scaling strategies, funding and legal aspects will be built, based on an assessment of assets, mission and legal structure of each partner. The establishment of venture capital funds (in both the private and public sectors) aligned with missions and the interaction with EU-wide crowdfunding platforms and sustainable financing³⁵ will also be promoted (Recs. 13 and 16). Taking into account that OpenRRIHubs are already working within the institutional structure of governmental structures, advocacy will be made towards coordination of European, national and regional funding streams (Rec. 15)³⁶. This will be supplemented by a training workshop on the topic of economic sustainability for the partners during the OpenRRIHub Summit closing conference.

Impact estimators: It is expected that by the implementation of OpenRRIHubs, RRI will be incorporated within governmental structures, using a cross-sectoral mission-oriented approach and stimulating bottom-up innovation, will lead to sustainable institutional change.

Consortia are expected to contribute to one or more of the MoRRI indicators and to contribute to one or more of the Sustainable Development Goals.

OpenRRIHubs will ensure contribution to the MoRRI indicators by synthesising best practice of their application in the development of the RRI institutional evaluation framework, which will lay the groundwork for the development of RRI action plan templates and subsequent tailored action plans for each territory.

Outputs: RRI institutional change evaluation framework based on synthesis of best practice in application of MORRI indicators at the territorial and institutional level (D2.1)

The table below highlights **OpenRRIHubs' expected impacts on MoRRI indicators** (Table 2.1) and our foreseen indicator focus for participating territories. It is worth noting that evaluation partner P3-QA is engaging closely with the SUPER-MoRRI project and will be looking for opportunities to integrate improved or extended indicators as appropriate for OpenRRIHubs.

35 https://ec.europa.eu/info/business-economy-euro/banking-and-finance/sustainable-finance_en

36 Recommendation 15: To maximise the impact of missions, the coordination of European, national and regional funding streams needs to be optimised.

Table 2.1 OpenRRIHubs' expected impacts on MoRRI indicators

MoRRI INDICATORS	OPENRRIHUBS
<p>We are expected to support development of more open, transparent and democratic regional R&I ecosystems in our partner territories to contribute to one or more of the MoRRI indicators. We will specifically address these MoRRI Indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GE2: Share of female researchers by sector • GE10: Share of female inventors and authors • SLSE-1: Importance of societal aspects of science in science curricula for 15-18 year olds • SLSE-4: Citizen Science activities in RPOs • PE-1: Models of public involvement in S&T decision- making • PE-2: Policy-oriented engagement with sci – ence • PE5: Public engagement performance mechanisms at the level of research institutions • OA1: Open access literature (OA1.1: Share of Open Access publications) • OA3: Social media outreach/ take up of Open Access Literature and open research data • GOV1: Use of science in policy-making 	<p>MoRRI indicator variables will be addressed as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GE2: Share of female researchers by sector • GE10: Share of female inventors and authors [Share of female researchers participating in OpenRRIHub activities, in project AB, local OpenRRIHubMBs, OpenRRIHub teams, and local stakeholders] • SLSE-1: Importance of societal aspects of science in science curricula for 15-18 year-olds [Working with territorial partners to track integration of RRI into the local science teaching, either inside or outside the classroom] • SLSE-4: Citizen Science activities in RPOs [Contributions of citizens to co-creation activities to be tracked and included in reporting] • PE-1: Models of public involvement in S&T decision-making [An evaluation instrument developed by QA for the TeRRIFICA project will be used to assess participatory process quality to shed light on the relative effectiveness of different public involvement approaches] • PE-2: Policy-oriented engagement with science [The project is designed to contribute to territorial policy-oriented outcomes. A dimension of the outputs measurement will be the extent and impact of such policy engagement stemming from project activities and outputs. This includes the number of policy engagement events completed in the project and the composition of the attendance at those events – including online] • PE-5: Public engagement performance mechanisms at the level of research and innovation institutions (The evaluation instrument adapted from TeRRIFICA assessing participatory process quality will indicate the effectiveness/performance of public engagement activities within the project). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OA-1 Open access literature (OA1.1: Share of Open Access publications) [All resources, products and solutions developed by OpenRRIHubs will be fully based on Open Standards and will be aligned with the H2020 Guidelines on Open Access] • OA-3: Social media outreach [retweets, likes, Facebook shares] /take up of Open Access Literature and open research data provided through the project [Project output measurement will include metrics on adherence to open access and open research data principles. We will measure the evolution in attitudes / practices pertaining to open access and open data] • GOV1: Use of science in policy-making [OpenRRIHubs will use R&I to tackle relevant society challenges, through a mission-oriented approach]

OpenRRIHubs and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals

OpenRRIHubs is anchored on the concept that Research & Innovation needs to move towards more explorative and maybe even high-risk forms of research and innovation, to create economic value and societal benefits. Such transition processes and a change-oriented agenda are to be guided by RRI principles and the Sustainable Development Goals. Based on “A framework for mission-oriented innovation policy roadmapping for the SDGs”³⁷ and “Fostering the Sustainable Development Goals in Horizon Europe”³⁸, the SDGs that we anticipate are the axis for OpenRRIHub missions and projects are listed below. OpenRRIHub will look at specific goals and targets for the activities and actions developed.

37 https://www.ucl.ac.uk/bartlett/public-purpose/sites/public-purpose/files/a_framework_for_mission-oriented_policy_roadmapping_for_the_sdgs_final.pdf

38 https://era.gv.at/object/document/3605/attach/Fostering_the_Sustainable_Development_Goals_in_Horizon_Europe_2019.pdf

Cancer

- *SDG3: Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages*

Climate change

- *SDG13: Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impact*
- *SDG12: Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns*

Healthy oceans

- *SDG14: Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development*

Climate-neutral cities

- *SDG11: Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable*
- *SDG7: Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all*

Healthy soil and food

- *SDG2: End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture*
- *SDG15: Protect, restore and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, and halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss*

The implementation of OpenRRIHubs will also actively contribute to the targets set in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development³⁹. Of the 17 SDGs, we shall incorporate four SDGs directly in our activities:

- *SDG4: Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all.* OpenRRIHubs will work with local partners to implement inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities through the project. In this manner, we address targets⁴⁰ 4.1, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5, and 4.7 of SDG4 through our activities and outreach to relevant audiences.
- *SDG5: Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls.* OpenRRIHubs activities will promote role model women R&I professions, OpenRRIHub will address the question of gender equality in science and technology. Our actions are directly relevant for Targets⁴¹ 5.1, 5.5 and 5.B of SDG5.
- *SDG16: Promote peaceful and inclusive societies.* By being established in communities that traditionally do not engage with R&I or do not bring RRI dimensions into the R&I processes due to various barriers (geographical location, socio-economic status, or minority ethnic group background), OpenRRIHubs will promote peaceful and inclusive societies.
- *SDG17: Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize the global partnership for sustainable development.* OpenRRIHub strategy and projects are grounded on partnerships between QH stakeholders. Our actions are directly relevant for Targets⁴² 17.6 and 17.17.

2.2. Measures to maximise impact

OpenRRIHubs emphasises measures based on the QH model of multi-stakeholder involvement. Four types of actors in social innovation processes are identifiable, all of whom are essential for success:

1. civil society, its organisations and actors
2. research, academia
3. government, administration
4. economy, business, industry, entrepreneurs, SMEs

In accordance with this, OpenRRIHubs will involve every group of actors and will assess the impact resulting from co-operation between these four groups. This approach can easily be adopted for territorial RRI policy implementation and will guide OpenRRIHubs' measures to maximise impact: all dissemination activities (see WP6) will be checked to see if they address all four actor groups with adequate means and adapted messages. Drivers and barriers in each of the actors' groups will be identified and their perspectives will, if necessary, be a matter of negotiation with the other groups. Impact can only be generated in a reflective process involving all stakeholder groups (covered in the ongoing iterative monitoring and validation activities of WP2).

39 <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/post2015/transformingourworld>

40 <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/sdg4#targets>

41 <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/sdg5#targets>

42 <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/sdg17#targets>

2.2.1. Dissemination and exploitation of results

Strategic approach

The goal of OpenRRIHub dissemination activities is to share the findings, lessons learned and RRI-based insights of the territorial projects with the wider scientific community, in particular networks, industry, education and policy. The project is designed to become a centre of reference particularly for organisations interested in RRI institutional change, where information on decision-making rooted in the RRI principles and mission-oriented strategies, outreach activities and ideas and competencies could be shared and promoted. As a part of this, OpenRRIHubs plays an innovative role and has the ability to generate new ideas and models for RRI-based decision-making activities. Dissemination facilitates exploitation, which is taken to mean the long-term uptake and utilisation of project outputs – namely, RRI institutional change – by ensuring that key actors in the territories are directly involved. To achieve this goal, OpenRRIHubs dissemination will share best practices on RRI institutional change and mission-oriented strategy, including all resources and guidelines. The development and implementation of the detailed exploitation and communication plan (led by WP6) will ensure widespread dissemination. OpenRRIHubs materials will be available in at least 6 languages (English, Dutch, Italian, Polish, Portuguese and Papiamentu). To maximise impact, OpenRRIHubs will explore a broad range of top-down and bottom-up approaches. OpenRRIHub results will be disseminated through a variety of existing channels, networks, and repositories targeting research and academia, education, industry, enterprises, SMEs, civil society organizations and actors, and governments (at local, regional, national and European level) (see Table 2.2). Consortium partner organisations have leading roles in all of these broader networks. This will enhance the impact of the dissemination. Where possible, dissemination will occur using digital platforms and tools. In addition to the significant territorial impact of local OpenRRIHubs, the OpenRRIHub project shall exploit its broad range of networks to attain as wide as possible a reach within countries, Europe and globally. Also, the project AB, local OpenRRIHubMB and local stakeholders will also play a fundamental role in disseminating activities and results to a wider audience through their extensive networks (either online or offline, e.g. by inviting OpenRRIHubs representatives in conferences or by distributing printed material (brochures) or enlarging the range of social network activities).

Table 2.2 Example of dissemination networks that OpenRRIHubs will exploit

NETWORK	NODES	RELEVANT PURPOSE OF THE NETWORK	TARGET AUDIENCE	LEAD
ECSITE	375	European network of science centres and museums	Science communication professionals	TCD
SCIENTIX	30	European community of science education	Teachers, researchers and project managers in science education, policy makers	TCD
Europlanet	30	Network linking planetary scientists from across Europe	Researchers in planetary science	ULEI
PCST – Public communication of science and technology network	2000	International network of public communication of science and technology	Science communications professionals, researchers, writers, web designers	ULEI
International Astronomical Union	12 400	International association of professional astronomers	Individual professional astronomers in dozens of countries worldwide	ULEI
European Physical Society	40	42 physics societies in Europe Largest network of physicists	Researchers	ULEI
European Academies (ALLEA)	60	59 Academies in more than 40 countries	Scientists in diverse scientific fields.	ULEI
Impact Hub Global	101, of which 42 in the EU	Link education and business	Social entrepreneurs	IHS
European Citizen Science Association	250	Network of Citizen Science with members and supporters from Europe and internationally.	Researchers, science educators, media, policy-makers, professionals from museums, NGOs, SMEs, citizens	ULEI

While dissemination activities will be primarily carried out in WP6, they are linked closely to and support activities carried out during other project phases, in particular dissemination through QH stakeholder engagement in the OpenRRIHub territories and exploitation (long-term sustainability of the OpenRRIHubs). Indeed, dissemination plans will be continually underpinned and informed by the stakeholder engagement strategy developed in WP5.

Step 1: At the start of the project – initial framework

The first stage of the Communication and Dissemination plan is to develop a strategy for communication, dissemination and exploitation to create awareness about project objectives and expected scientific contribution, based on the stakeholder engagement strategies developed for each territory. This will include identifying stakeholders in and beyond Europe that are likely to benefit from the insights and innovations of the project (target groups), identifying which kinds of insights and innovations will be of most relevance to stakeholders of different types (addressing message), as well as identifying the appropriate and most effective dissemination channels for each group (means of engagement). The identification of these target groups and their needs will inform the development of the design and content of information products developed throughout the project. The overall dissemination framework will be implemented and continuously updated during the lifetime of the project based on the continuous stakeholder engagement and participatory process feedback loops enabled by our ongoing monitoring and evaluation strategy (WP2), to ensure that communication is understandable, credible and relevant.

Step 2: During the project – Dissemination and exploitation activities

The next step focuses also on the support of the activities of the OpenRRIHubs in each territory. Below, we outline the main (open source) OpenRRIHub products and activities are identified as main assets for exploitation during, but also after, the project timeline.

OpenRRIHub Outcomes for exploitation

- OpenRRIHub Blueprint, which includes a detailed plan of action, financial assets, organisational structure, a clear design of distribution of responsibilities, decision-making processes, gender equity and inclusion recommendations
- OpenRRIHub digital platform, with best practices, resources, materials, guidelines, OpenRRIHub Blueprint, and dedicated sections to each Territorial Partner
- Training workshops and guidelines about RRI institutional change and QH engagement
- Toolkit for setting-up a mission-oriented strategy (it will be part of the OpenRRI Blueprint)
- OpenRRIHub co-creation sessions
- Open and citizen-oriented bi-directional communication products to share R&I selected projects (process, results, outcomes)
- OpenRRIHub sustainability plans (it will be part of the OpenRRI Blueprint)
- OpenRRIHub evaluation/research results to inform policy and QH governance (through research publications in open access journals and policy-briefs)
- Toolkit about SwafS-14—Supporting the development of territorial Responsible Research and Innovation—legacy synthesising learning from across all SwafS14 projects for the benefit of territorial scholars, students and policy-makers (it will be part of the OpenRRI Blueprint)

All the OpenRRIHub communication materials will be made available on the project website. This will have sections dedicated to each territory and will be translated in, at least, 6 languages (English, Dutch, Italian, Polish, Portuguese and Papiamentu), and will be disseminated via the appropriate channels (Table 2.3). Throughout the project, findings will be sought to be disseminated at RRI-related conferences in order to establish the project as an important player in territorial RRI development. Further, as the project progresses and crucial insights into territorial RRI development emerge, policy briefs will be developed on best practice in developing RRI institutional changes in an open and inclusive way at the territorial level. Dissemination activities will be tracked via the production of annual dissemination and exploitation reports, detailing complete and planned communication activities to consortium members, stakeholders and the EC.

At the end of the project, a final OpenRRIHub Summit will bring together all partners and key stakeholders to consolidate the outcomes of the project, share best practices and discuss the sustainability and legacy of OpenRRIHubs.

Step 3: After the project – interconnecting R&I and Governance contributions

The OpenRRIHubs will provide a basis for lasting interaction after the project has ended. This community and partnerships developed will ensure OpenRRIHubs Outcomes important organisations and networks through proactive cross-

network communication, ensuring a sustainable result. Publications in scientific open-access journals will feed results and insights about territorial RRI institutional change in the innovation processes into the scientific discourse. Other dissemination activities after the project will include the presentation of the findings at scientific conferences. Target groups, media channels and messages might differ in the different countries, thus a broad variety of promoters will be aimed for.

Exploitation plan beyond the lifetime of the project

The exploitation plan aims to ensure that OpenRRIHub insights, findings and results are implemented in practice beyond the lifetime of the project. Exploitation will be an on-going process throughout the project duration in order to capture emerging trends and new information from the project activities, to fine tune the value proposition of the OpenRRIHubs, and ensure sustainability beyond the project's lifetime. Thus, the iterative approach to monitoring and evaluation in WP2 will feed into exploitation plans, and is consolidated in long-term exploitation plans for each territory and for European cooperation (WP6). The exploitation plan also supports how other relevant stakeholders – beyond the territories – will accept our findings and implement them. It will describe drivers and barriers for each actor group of QH actors as a means to improve the implementation of RRI policies in environmental decision-making contexts.

- *Territorial RRI network exploitation:* By integrating the different stakeholders into one OpenRRIHub, acting in a co-created process to participate in RRI-based decision-making, the network will feel responsible for their activities and will develop also structures within each hub. The sharing of understanding, the exchange of ideas and the common work will elaborate the network further to a sustainable community that will last long beyond the project. It is also expected that these established communities will launch further (small scale) projects, initiatives and (short term) activities.
- *Capacity-building exploitation:* OpenRRIHubs ensures that the valuable insights, techniques, methodologies and outcomes developed by the project are made available, accessible and useful to those working in relevant fields and topics through the creation of carefully structured online course content designed to be freely available through Creative Commons licensing.
- *Policy exploitation:* At the core of the OpenRRIHubs project is the objective to embed long-term RRI institutional change in territorial governance to engage the QH and follow more open and inclusive practices in the policy development process. The action plans co-created for each territory will detail the ways in which these organisational policy changes can be implemented.
- *Economic sustainability:* Through the work detailed in WP7, economic sustainability for each territorial partner will be ensured through the development of a business model format that includes market study and segmentation, business plan, social impact, scaling strategies, funding and legal aspects for each. This will be precluded by an analysis of the assets, mission and legal structure of each partner in order to identify a tailored strategy.

Open Research Data and Knowledge Management, Protection and Exploitation

When it comes to publishing or making collected data available, and if not contrary to the legitimate academic or commercial interests of the partner(s) involved, such data will also be provided in open access to be reached via the project website. Individuals and organisations making use of the website will be encouraged to add their experiences, and to connect with each other. This website is to be managed by P5-SN and P1-ULEI, which will be placed to make the data accessible through its global networks. OpenRRIHub will generate both quantitative and qualitative data from the participants which will be collected and stored using encrypted digital devices. The consortium is well aware of the responsibilities in proceeding personal data and all partners have worked with personal data before. All data protection issues will be addressed in a data management plan to be implemented by the project management (WP1). The data management plan will define procedures and responsibilities regarding the processing of personal data and will make sure that the plan complies with ethical principles. Details are also given in the Ethics section of this proposal (Section 5). All data will be collected anonymously and stored according to the European rules on Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020 and in compliance with EU General Data Protection Regulation. All data collected will be archived and curated using a standard data management plan that adheres to the European Commission's guidelines on FAIR data management⁴³.

All the OpenRRIHub publications, research, data and products will follow closely the guidelines on open access to scientific publications and research data in Horizon 2020 provided by the European Commission. Products and resources will be open source and where relevant produced using a Creative Commons License (Attribution-Non-Commercial-Share Alike 4.0 International). This follows closely the recommendations from the European Commission on Open Access⁴⁴. Where possible, we shall also make the source files publicly available in common open repositories. Research produced by OpenRRIHub will be shared through peer-reviewed, open access publications, as well as publishing open data on the Zenodo platform founded by CERN.

43 https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

44 https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf

2.2.2. Communication activities

Communication activities within OpenRRIHubs are actions carried out to provide targeted information to multiple, non-specialist audiences in a strategic and effective manner. Communication provides support to, but does not replace more technical and target-oriented dissemination and exploitation activities. A specific challenge is identified here: the knowledge about social, environmental and economic impacts of environmental decision-making should be increased to build up an informed public debate on comprehensible facts and raise awareness, but this has to be done **without “overloading” the audiences** and making the issues too complex. Communication must be able to be easily understood and engaging for non-specialist audiences. OpenRRIHubs recognises these issues and activities as particularly important in the context of developing open and inclusive participatory processes of policy development which involves citizens.

To translate the technical and scientific language of OpenRRIHubs into information of relevance to audiences’ daily lives, the messages must propose the outcomes of OpenRRIHubs to a wide public. Messages should demonstrate the importance and relevance of the project to citizens’ everyday lives, to solving some of today’s main environmental challenges. Messages will focus on practical benefits of RRI application, in terms of socio-economic development and benefits to different groups of the population through: competitiveness of enterprises that make up the fabric of our economy; anticipation, reflection and risk management in producing innovations; encouraging science education; direct involvement in change, through public engagement.

The sections below describe all OpenRRIHub target audiences, dissemination channels and the measures that will be applied to reach them. The sections also describe a set of communication products that will be created to achieve the expected impact for each specific target group.

Government, administration

OpenRRIHubs are part of the governmental institutional structures, and their place inside the respective structures, together with the distribution of responsibilities and decision-making processes will be clear since the beginning of the project (led by WP3). As such, OpenRRIHubs will have direct connections with the executive power offices as well as different governmental departments. In order to maintain a regular and open communication process, project management & internal communication tools will be used on a daily-basis (e.g. Basecamp), as well as emails. In addition, every 4 months a newsletter will be sent with updates about the project. The elements of this target group will also participate in the Training workshops about RRI institutional change and QH engagement, as well as in the co-creation sessions. For this target group, main relevant OpenRRIHub assets are: OpenRRIHub Blueprint, OpenRRIHub digital platform, Training workshops and guidelines, Toolkit about mission-oriented strategy, OpenRRIHub co-creation sessions, communication products about the R&I selected projects, OpenRRIHub sustainability plans, OpenRRIHub evaluation/research results, Toolkit about SwafS14 legacy.

Academia/research

One of the Territorial Partners is part of a University (P1-ULEI) and two of the RRI Experts are also part of universities (P1-ULEI, P2-TCD) and research networks (see Table 2.2). In addition, academia representatives will be part of the local OpenRRIHubMBs. Through these partnerships, OpenRRIHubs will reach out and involve university educators and researchers in the co-development and implementation of OpenRRIHub activities throughout the OpenRRIHub network, and will facilitate collaborations between researchers and local enterprises. Specifically, OpenRRIHub will exploit existing mailing lists (e.g. Leiden University internal mailing list and alumni mailing list), websites of partner research networks research unions (e.g. European Physical Society, International Astronomical Union), and academies of science and humanities (e.g. ALLEA) and leverage participation at relevant conferences, to reach this target audience. OpenRRIHubs partners (P1-ULEI, P2-TCD) also run training for scientists involved in science communication activities (for example JCOM Masterclasses⁴⁵, Thesis in Three⁴⁶ and master’s programmes in Science Communication⁴⁷), and will disseminate OpenRRIHub project processes and results in such occasions in the years to come. OpenRRIHub will send email, newsletters, publish updates on existing websites, develop an active presence on social media and disseminate posters and leaflets at relevant events. For this target group, main relevant OpenRRIHub assets are: OpenRRIHub Blueprint, OpenRRIHub digital platform, Training workshops and guidelines, Toolkit about mission-oriented strategy, OpenRRIHub co-creation sessions, communication products about the R&I selected projects, OpenRRIHub sustainability plans, OpenRRIHub evaluation/research results, Toolkit about SwafS-14—Supporting the development of territorial Responsible Research and Innovation—legacy.

Industry, SMEs, business, entrepreneurs

Three of the RRI Experts are SMEs (P3-QA, P4-IHS, P5-SN) and are part of networks of social entrepreneurs. In addition, representatives from industry and SMEs will also be part of the local OpenRRIHubMBs. These partnerships will constitute very relevant networking points to involve more entrepreneurs and professionals from industry, SMEs and business fields in the

45 <https://jcom.sissa.it/>

46 <https://thesisin3.com/>

47 <https://www.universiteitleiden.nl/en/science/science-communication-and-society>

co-development and implementation of OpenRRIHub activities. OpenRRIHub will send email, newsletters, publish updates on existing websites, develop an active presence on social media and disseminate posters and leaflets at relevant events. For this target group, main relevant OpenRRIHub assets are: OpenRRIHub Blueprint, OpenRRIHub digital platform, Training workshops and guidelines, Toolkit about mission-oriented strategy, OpenRRIHub co-creation sessions, communication products about the R&I selected projects, OpenRRIHub sustainability plans, OpenRRIHub evaluation/research results, Toolkit about SwafS-14—Supporting the development of territorial Responsible Research and Innovation—legacy.

Civil society, its organisations and actors

Civil society representatives will be part of the local OpenRRIHubMBs and these partnerships will constitute very relevant networking points to involve more civil society organizations and actors in the co-development and implementation of OpenRRIHub activities. OpenRRIHubs will also connect with citizen movements, namely environmental NGOs, workers and under-represented groups. For this target group, main relevant OpenRRIHub assets are: OpenRRIHub Blueprint, OpenRRIHub digital platform, Training workshops and guidelines, Toolkit about mission-oriented strategy, OpenRRIHub co-creation sessions, communication products about the R&I selected projects, OpenRRIHub sustainability plans, OpenRRIHub evaluation/research results, Toolkit about SwafS-14—Supporting the development of territorial Responsible Research and Innovation—legacy.

Communication Channels identified to reach the various target groups are summarised below (Table 2.3). All will be carried out during the full project duration to address the various target audiences depending on specific characteristics. The table also provides the target numbers expected in terms of outputs / reach.

Table 2.3 Vehicles for creating impact

COMMUNICATION CHANNEL	CONCRETE DESCRIPTION	NUMBERS REACHED	PARTNERS INVOLVED
OpenRRIHubs website (public site)	Website providing initial information, content, announcement for partners' outreach activities.	<i>Estimated:</i> average visits per month from Year 2 onwards >1.000.	All partner, led by P5-SN
OpenRRIHubs print products (Reports)	Distributed to various stakeholders.	<i>Estimated:</i> > 1.000 distributed.	All partner, led by P5-SN
Partners' websites	Information on OpenRRIHubs and in specific territories available on existing partners websites.	<i>Estimated:</i> > 500.000 people reached (based on unique page views).	All partner, led by P5-SN
Partners communities and partner networks	OpenRRIHubs will use their existing networks and newsletters to disseminate the project activities and outcomes and to inform relevant stakeholders.	<i>Estimated:</i> > 100.000 people reached.	All partner, led by P5-SN
Partner social networks	Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and, Instagram reaching out to their target groups and existing followers.	<i>Estimated:</i> Twitter: Total of 350000 Facebook: 176000 Followers LinkedIn: 77000 followers	All partner, led by P5-SN
Media (including TV, Press)	At least 4 press releases during the project, OpenRRIHub project announced; Announcement of the Missions for each territory; Selected R&i projects; Final projects outcomes. Press releases will be distributed online and using the Press Information channels from partner organisations. Relevant media will be invited to all the OpenRRIHub activities.	10 000 (Media reach) around 1 000 000 media engagements.	All partners, led by P5-SN

In summary, based on the data from our consortium's previous projects the expected number of representatives from governments, academia, industry, civil society organizations and citizens to be reached by OpenRRIHub communication initiatives over 3 years is about 300 000 individuals.

3. Implementation

3.1. Work plan – Work packages and deliverables

OpenRRIHubs implementation combines a set of specific tasks and components necessary for achieving the strategic objectives set in Section 1 with the skills, competencies and networks provided by the consortium partners. OpenRRIHub is planned as a 36-month project and is divided into 8 Work Packages (WP). All the WPs support a high-quality implementation through a credible approach and efficient coordination and support measures (Figure 3.1). The work package content is detailed in the WP description tables to be found in Tables 3.1a.

Fig 3.1. Overview of OpenRRIHub WPs and their main concepts and components. All the OpenRRIHub WPs will feed into the OpenRRIHubs “on the ground” impacts and, in the long-term, their legacy.

Table 3.1 a: List of work packages

WORK PACKAGE No	WORK PACKAGE TITLE	LEAD PARTICIPANT No	LEAD PARTICIPANT SHORT NAME	PERSON MONTHS	START MONTH	END MONTH
1	Management & Coordination	1	ULEI	19	1	36
2	Monitoring, Evaluation and Reflective Practice	3	QA	42	1	36
3	Open RRI Hub Structures, Strategies and Protocols	4	IHS	51	1	12
4	Designing and Implementation of Open RRI Hubs Action Plans for Territorial R & I Ecosystems	1	ULEI	41	1	36
5	Stakeholder engagement and mutual learning within the Quadruple Helix framework applying open and inclusive approaches	2	TCD	52	1	36

6	Broadening impact through communication, dissemination and exploitation	6	SN	39	1	36
7	Advocacy, Sustainability & Legacy	10	FL	37	1	36
8	Ethics		ULEI	0.5	1	36
				TOTAL PERSON-MONTHS	281.5	

Table 3.1b. OpenRRIhub Work packages overview

WORK PACKAGE NUMBER	1	LEAD BENEFICIARY	ULEI (and ALL the WP)					
WORK PACKAGE TITLE	Management & Coordination							
Participant number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Short name of participant	ULEI	TCD	QA	IHS	SN	MFCR	AIRC	FL
Person months per participant	5	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Start month	1	End month	36					

Objectives

The main objective is to coordinate the activities and to maintain an efficient relation between the project partners, stakeholders and the European Commission. In particular, this Work Package intends to achieve the highest standards of quality of deliverables, and to do so on time and within budget. The specific objectives are:

- Set up the management infrastructure of the project
- Manage the project overall to achieve the project objectives and the requirements of the call
- Ensure the implementation of project activities on time and as described in the proposal
- Address potential issues and take corrective actions if necessary
- To oversee and assist the project's progress
- To carry out an on-going evaluation of the effectiveness of each work package for the duration of the project and ensure that procedures are in place to implement changes if necessary.

Description of work

The work package is led by P1-ULEI. All partners are involved in the project management, internal communications activities, and the production of deliverables and reports.

Task 1.1. Set up and run the management infrastructure (M1-M36, Lead: P1-ULEI with inputs from all other partners)

- Produce the common management framework: Organise and set up internal communication tools and activities: regular consortium meetings, internal work package meetings, communications platforms (e.g.: Basecamp or Slack), document-sharing platform (e.g: G Suite), innovation management tools (e.g: Viima).
- Set-up an innovation management plan: OpenRRIHub will produce expected and unexpected innovative products and approaches. These will be captured and disseminated through the network through a specific innovation management plan.
- Develop and implement Intellectual Property Rights Management Plan suitable for wide dissemination to internal and external stakeholders and conforming, wherever possible, with the principles of Open Science through an appropriate use of licenses.
- Constitute the project advisory board (AB) including enterprise representatives, gender and diversity experts and research organisations representative.
- Monitor the gender dimension in all aspects of the OpenRRIHub (from management structures to activities)
- Monitor risk and quality of implementation.

Task 1.2. Set up and run the project monitoring system (M1-M36, Lead: P1-ULEI with inputs and participation from all other partners)

- Monitor each work package progress.
- Identify and address potential issues, take or propose corrective actions when necessary.
- Ensure the submission of all deliverables of the project on time.
- Coordinate the implementation and submission of the project periodic reports.
- Make sure that the project objectives are achieved with sufficient attention on the requirements of the grant agreement.
- Liaise and coordinate with European Commission and other relevant European institutions.
- Work closely with WP2: Evaluation leader to ensure that the identified issues in the implementation of the project are tackled accordingly.

Task 1.3 Prepare, administer and chair consortium meetings (M1-M36, Lead: P1-ULEI with input and participation from all other partners, in particular the WP leaders)

- Organisation of kick-off meeting in M1 for all partners to be organised/hosted by P1-ULEI.
- Organisation of additional face-to-face meeting (M12) for all partners to be hosted in one the partners premises.
- Organisation of Advisory Board virtual meeting every 6 months.

Deliverables

- D1.1 OpenRRIHub Coordination Plan (M3): This plan includes the common project framework including Quality Assurance Plan, Risk Management Plan and Data Management Plan.
- D1.2 First periodic report (M12): report on activity implementation after Year 1 of the project.
- D1.3 Second periodic report (M24): report on activity implementation after Year 2 of the project.
- D1.4 Final Report (M36): report on activity implementation of the project.

If necessary, these reports, after discussion with the EC, can be integrated in the regular reporting periods.

Milestones

- M1.1 Consortium Meeting #1 (M2)
- M1.2 Consortium Meeting #2 (M20)

WORK PACKAGE NUMBER	2	LEAD BENEFICIARY	QA					
WORK PACKAGE TITLE	Monitoring, Evaluation and Reflective Practice							
Participant number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Short name of participant	ULEI	TCD	QA	IHS	SN	MFCR	AIRC	FL
Person months per participant	4	6	14	3	3	4	4	4
Start month	1	End month	36					

Objectives

WP2 aims to lay the groundwork for effectively engaging and mobilizing territorial stakeholders to foster long-term integration of RRI principles of open and inclusive innovation into R&I ecosystems by delivering participatory process evaluation and organisational impact evaluation.

- To assess challenges and opportunities to increase RRI awareness and acceptability.
- To facilitate evidence-based decision-making on how best to integrate RRI within participating territories underpinned by effective ongoing evaluation and monitoring.

- Develop the capabilities of participating organisations to conduct their work following processes that are socially responsible, in line with established best practice.
- To evaluate enhancing RRI capacity amongst partner and associated institutions.
- To deliver ‘just in time’ insights that can be used to adapt the implementation approach while it is still underway.
- To deliver an evaluation framework, which includes stakeholder needs, interests and attitudes.
- To evaluate empirically the impact of RRI institutional change and stakeholder engagement-oriented project interventions, including issues such as drivers and barriers.
- To synthesize best practice from other related H2020 SwafS projects.
- To develop findings about best practice that can inform the work of other EU projects and institutions.

Description of work

The work package is led by P3-QA. All partners are involved in effectively engaging and mobilizing territorial stakeholders to foster long-term integration of RRI principles of open and inclusive innovation into R&I eco-systems.

Task 2.1 Synthesis of best practice in application of of MoRRI indicators at the territorial and institutional level: RRI institutional change evaluation framework (M1-M6, Lead: P3-QA with input from all other partners, in particular Territorial partners)

- Integrate the latest insights from SUPER-MoRRI project and other RRI indicators
- Conduct full review across the SwafS portfolio (but especially previously funded SwafS-14 projects)
- Interview relevant experts as needed
- Identify ‘lessons learned’ and effective measurement approaches, instruments and items that can be adapted for use in this project and provide a valuable legacy resource stemming from SwafS work, taking advantage of the timing of this project at the very end of the SwafS H2020 funding cycle.
- Define indicators framework for OpenRRIHub project

Task 2.2: Developing evidence-based RRI capacity across the consortium with associated evaluation (M6-M36, Lead: P3-QA with input and participation all other partners)

- Adapting existing methodologically tested evaluation instruments developed through the RRING (rring.eu), GRRIP (grrip.eu) and TeRRIFICA (terrifica.eu) SwafS projects by Qualia Analytics in collaboration with others, conduct evaluation of ‘as is’ RRI capacity and practices in partner organisations, especially the territorial partners, to identify gaps and critical needs for training and mentoring by RRI expert partners (M6)
- Organize training workshops with partners, tailored to the formative evaluation findings to achieve maximum impact to build capacity (M7) to follow processes that are socially responsible, in line with established best practice (including relating to gender equality, open access, ethics and other RRI dimensions and/or SDGS), drawing on external expert speakers as needed.
- Conduct a second round of evaluation with matching measures to track progress and identify where further capacity building is needed (M21).
- Organize a second (online) capacity building workshop with all partners (M22).
- Conduct a final round of evaluation to provide a summative assessment of progress over the course of the project, and highlights lessons learned and steps still remaining for participating RPOs (M32).
- Provide ongoing mentorship and support process to continue developing capacity on an ‘as needed’ basis. (M7-M36)

Task 2.3 Assessment of the impact of OpenRRIHubs at organisational level (M6-M36, Lead:P3-QA with input and participation from all partners)

- Organise workshop(s) with SwafS-14 project partners who have conducted impact assessment in prior years and past and ongoing projects to synthesise learning and integrate into OpenRRIHubs work and legacy.
- Build on impact measurement tools and methodologies developed by previously funded projects under this funding call, including TeRRIFICA (where QA also leads on evaluation).
- Develop evaluation frameworks for the project
- Implement ongoing monitoring and evaluation practices including participatory process evaluation and organisational impact evaluation
- Assess the progress of achieving stakeholder and citizen ownership and partnership development
- Evaluate the impact of RRI institutional change and stakeholder engagement-oriented project interventions in the context of environmental decision-making.

Deliverables

- D2.1: Synthesis of best practices in application of MoRRI indicators at the territorial and institutional level and RRI institutional change evaluation framework (M6)
- D2.2: Lessons learned from citizen and engagement collaborative workshops and related work (M36): Report on Capacity Building activities, outputs and outcomes
- D2.3: RRI institutional change impact evaluation report (M36): Report on assessment of the impact of OpenRRIHubs on partner institutions' RRI capacity and their role in engaging stakeholders in the territorial R&I ecosystems

Milestones

- M2.1 Evaluation frameworks for impact evaluation of OpenRRIHubs in the local communities (M9)

WORK PACKAGE NUMBER	3	LEAD BENEFICIARY	Impact Hub					
WORK PACKAGE TITLE	Open RRI Hub Structures, Strategies and Protocols							
Participant number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Short name of participant	ULEI	TCD	QA	IHS	SN	MFCR	AIRC	FL
Person months per participant	7	3	3	14	3	7	7	7
Start month	1	End month	12					

Objectives

The main objective of this WP is to establish and maintain the OpenRRIHub structures within the host institutions institutional organization and in relation to the QH societal stakeholders, community partners, and wider society.

- To understand internal and external context to host institutions
- To produce a stakeholders' analysis, maps and database
- To establish each OpenRRIHub Structure, Strategies and Protocol
- To establish Local OpenRRIHubMBs (with representatives from different QH societal stakeholders).

Description of work

The work package is led by P4-IHS. All partners are involved, in particular the territorial partners. This WP intends to provide the territorial partners with the tools to understand their local context and to most effectively and sustainably establish the OpenRRIHubs within the organizational structure of their host institution.

Task 3.1 Context analysis, maps and databases of the RRI Territorial Partners, including external relations (M1-M6, Lead: P4-IHS, with input and participation from all partners, in particular territorial partners)

- Understand internal contexts of host institutions, namely organizational structure, distribution of responsibilities, decision-making processes
- Mapping stakeholders, relations with collaborators and pre-existing projects

Task 3.2 Stakeholder upstream assessment of key needs, interests, expectations and concerns (M1-M8, Lead: P4-IHS with input and participation of all territorial partners)

- Conduct empirical assessment of stakeholder needs, interests, expectations and concerns relevant to the project to lay the groundwork for local QH involvement. Stakeholders include elements of the host institutions and external partners.
- This research will be conducted with carefully designed and piloted tools, both qualitative and quantitative, including interviews, focus groups, or other techniques such as the Delphi Method and co-design thinking processes, in order to allow comparability across the different project regions.

Task 3.3 Development of OpenRRIHub Blueprint: Structures, Strategies and Protocols for establishment of the OpenRRIHubs and OpenRRIHubMB (M1-M12, Lead: P4-IHS with input and participation of all territorial partners)

- Using the information from Tasks 3.1 and 3.2, each local OpenRRIHub will set up a response strategy, with a detailed plan of action, encompassing a strategy and timeline, financial assets, organizational structure with a clear distribution of responsibilities, network flow between groups/departments/people and decision-making processes. This will be included in the OpenRRIHub Blueprint.
- Establishment of the OpenRRIHubMB management structure, based on the information from Tasks 3.1 and 3.2, which will include representatives from the QH (government, academia, industry and civil society). This will also be included in the OpenRRIHub Blueprint.

Deliverables

- D3.1 Report about each Territorial Partner organizational structure and stakeholders (M6)
- D3.2 Report with stakeholder mapping in each Territorial Partner (M8)
- D3.3 OpenRRIHub Blueprint, with the Structures, Strategies and Protocols for establishment of the OpenRRIHubs and OpenRRIHubMB (M12)

WORK PACKAGE NUMBER	4	LEAD BENEFICIARY	ULEI					
WORK PACKAGE TITLE	Designing and Implementation of Open RRI Hubs Action Plans for Territorial R & I Ecosystems							
Participant number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Short name of participant	ULEI	TCD	QA	IHS	SN	MFCR	AIRC	FL
Person months per participant	7	3	3	4	3	7	7	7
Start month	6	End month	36					

Objectives

The main objective of this WP is to support the territorial partners with the resources to set-up a mission-oriented strategy in their territories, in collaboration with local stakeholders, by following three sequential stages:

- Co-creation of mission roadmaps
- Implementation of missions by using a bottom-up approach
- Co-assessment of the R&I Mission-Oriented pilot projects, with local stakeholders

Description of work

The work package is led by P1-ULEI. All partners are involved, in particular the territorial partners. This WP will develop the tools for setting-up a mission-oriented strategy, and, together with WP5, will provide partners with the necessary training and support.

Task 4.1 Development of guidelines for co-designing Mission Roadmaps (M6-M12, Lead: P1-ULEI with input and participation of all WP leaders)

- Literature review about Mission-oriented approaches
- Development of protocols that guide the design of a Mission Roadmap, and that will include identifying relevant societal challenges and transforming them into concrete measurable missions, that are framed in a cross-sector manner, bringing in multiple actors.

Task 4.2 Development of guidelines for establishing Open Calls for R&I Mission-oriented pilot projects in each Territorial Partner Location (M9-M15, Lead: P1-ULEI with input and participation of all WP leaders)

- Development of the Rules for the Open Calls for R&I Missions-oriented projects, that include the objecti-

ves, evaluation criteria, eligibility, amount of funding.

- Based on the co-created Missions Roadmaps for each Territorial Partner Location (D4.4 Mission Roadmaps), adapting the Open Call Rules to each Territorial Partner location, according to the defined mission and respective sectors that will be involved.

Task 4.3 Development of guidelines for the assessment of the R&I Mission-oriented pilot projects in collaboration with OpenRRIHUBs (M12-M18, Lead: P1-ULEI with input and participation of all WP leaders)

- Development of the set of criteria to monitor and assess the selected R&I Mission-Oriented pilot projects in collaboration with QH to strengthen the alignment between the processes and outcomes of the R&I projects and societal needs and expectations.

Task 4.4 Implementation of the Mission-oriented strategy (M12-M36, Lead: P1-ULEI; Co-lead: P2-TCD, with input and participation of all territorial partners)

- Organization of co-creation sessions to co-design the Mission Roadmaps with local stakeholders, in each Territorial Partner location
- Launching the Open Call for R&I Mission-Oriented Pilot Project
- Selecting the R&I Mission-Oriented Pilot Projects that will be implemented in each Territorial Partner Location together with the OpenRRIHUB
- Co-monitoring and assessing the selected R&I pilot projects together with the OpenRRIHUB

Deliverables

- D4.1 Guidelines for co-designing Mission Roadmaps (M12)
- D4.2 Guidelines for the establishment of the R&I Open Calls (M15)
- D4.3 Guidelines for the co-assessment of R&I Mission-oriented pilot projects (M18)
- D4.4 Mission Roadmaps (M15)
- D4.5 Report about the co-assessment of the R&I Mission-oriented pilot projects (M36)

Milestones

- M4.1 Selected R&I Mission-oriented pilot projects (M18)

WORK PACKAGE NUMBER	5	LEAD BENEFICIARY	TCD					
WORK PACKAGE TITLE	Stakeholder engagement and mutual learning within the Quadruple Helix framework applying open and inclusive approaches							
Participant number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Short name of participant	ULEI	TCD	QA	IHS	SN	MFCR	AIRC	FL
Person months per participant	7	12	5	4	3	7	7	7
Start month		End month						

Objectives

The main objectives of this WP are to support territorial partners with the tools and training to implement an effective and evidence-based QH engagement strategy in their territories, while setting up a mission-oriented approach:

- Enable the application of best practice in stakeholder engagement in the participating territories to foster a healthy R&I ecosystem of open and inclusive practices and policies.
- Build QH engagement capacity of OpenRRIHUBs, and respective governmental structures, to ensure effective participation of QH in the process and local 'ownership' of the project, namely throughout the co-creation, co-implementation and co-assessment of missions

- Convene mutual learning meetings between project partners, and document ‘lessons learned’ along the way to establish institutional learning and share insights with other ongoing EU projects.

Description of work

This work package is led by P2-TCD, with participation from all partners. QH framework is essential to an effective R&I ecosystem: territorial partners must mobilise their local stakeholders to co-create, co-implement and co-assess the missions. This WP will be performed in collaboration with WP4.

Task 5.1: Developing and Implement Evidence-based QH Open and Inclusive Engagement Strategy (M1-M36, Lead: P2-TCD with input and participation of P1-ULEI)

- Critically review previous and current EU (and beyond) projects which have successfully integrated the QH into efforts to develop an open and inclusive R&I ecosystem at the territorial level.
- Develop a toolkit for QH Open and Inclusive Engagement Strategy, to support development of RRI within participating territories, through practical support, ‘critical friend’ role, etc., allowing to assess questions such as:
 - Has each type of QH stakeholder been adequately represented
 - Has stakeholder engagement been meaningful and productive, enjoyable and fulfilling?
 - Has the engagement resulted in R&I collaboration? Is QH platform fit for purpose?
 - Did each QH participant achieve its engagement objectives?
- Support the implementation within Territorial Partners.

Task 5.2 Building QH engagement capacity to support OpenRRIHubs implementing a Mission-oriented strategy in their territories (M1-M36, Lead: P2-TCD; Co-lead: P1-ULEI, with input and participation of all partners)

- Organize a training workshop for all partners, in collaboration with WP4, to support OpenRRIHubs implementing co-creation workshops in their territories for mission co-design with local stakeholders.
- Providing continuous mentoring to OpenRRIHubs throughout the project to support them engaging QH in an open and inclusive way during the whole mission-oriented strategy process

Task 5.3 Fostering mutual learning processes and activities amongst consortium partners, with a focus on OpenRRIHubs and respective governmental structures (M6-M36, Lead: P2-TCD with input and participation of all partners)

- Organize mutual learning visits between consortium partners, namely across the participating territories. Whenever possible, these mutual learning visits will involve the participation of elements of the partner’s governmental structures, to share experiences, challenges and successes.
- Organize periodic structured sharing calls during the implementation of the project

Deliverables

- D5.1 Toolkit for QH Open and Inclusive Engagement Strategy (M12)
- D5.2 Training workshop about QH Engagement Strategy (M13)
- D5.3 Publication (white paper, report, guide) with Lessons learnt from the mutual learning processes (M34)

Milestones

- M5.1 Mutual Learning visits and calls for mutual learning (M14)

WORK PACKAGE NUMBER	6	LEAD BENEFICIARY	SN					
WORK PACKAGE TITLE	Broadening impact through communication, dissemination and exploitation							
Participant number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Short name of participant	ULEI	TCD	QA	IHS	SN	MFCR	AIRC	FL
Person months per participant	5	3	3	3	16	3	3	3
Start month	1	End month	36					

Objectives

The main objective of this WP is to embed responsible and impactful storytelling into the project, document the learning process and disseminate insights and experiences to a wider community, ensuring that findings and innovations from the project will have the broadest possible impact beyond the scope of project partners and participants:

- Understand and map communication needs and practices across consortium participants specific for the OpenRRIHubs project,
- Frame the project's communication and dissemination strategy in a co-design process,
- Identify stakeholders in and beyond Europe that are likely to benefit from the insights and innovations of the project,
- Create supporting material needed for external stakeholders to learn about the project in general, as well as in preparation for understanding the specific results and innovations to be shared – including resources created for internal training for the participating institutions.
- Create suitable information products for dissemination for insights, experiences and innovations derived from the mission phases.

Description of work

The WP is led by P5-SN. All partners are involved in supporting the dissemination effort and providing input for the deliverables.

Task 6.1: Development and Implementation of communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy for stakeholder and wider citizen engagement and dissemination (M1-M36, Lead: P5-SN with input and participation from all partners, namely on localisation support).

- Development of a strategy for successful stakeholder and wider citizen engagement for each regional OpenRRIHub partner, including:
 - Identification of target groups for dissemination of project innovations and results
 - Visual communication language (project logo and brand book) and layout for editorial and digital publications
 - Setting up digital presence channels including website and social media.
 - Materials for OpenRRIHub Final Summit
- Implement the OpenRRIHub communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy

Task 6.2 Implementation of engagement and dissemination strategy within participating territories through stakeholder and citizen engagement workshops (M6-M16, Lead: P5-SN, Co-lead: P7-AIRC, with contributions from all partners)

- Support collaborative citizen and stakeholder engagement for each of the territorial partner, which includes:
 - liaising with other WPs to provide expert input and support in the involvement of stakeholders and other citizens.
 - support the analysis of the needs and opportunities to involve stakeholders and other citizens as upstream as feasible in institutional change processes instigated by the project, in order to widen the pool of actively engaged stakeholders, leveraging the involvement and support of local entities beyond the partners already engaged in the project
 - provision of expert support, facilitation expertise and analysis guidance for at least one upstream stakeholder and citizen engagement workshop per study region and one downstream (focusing on dissemination of project results) stakeholder and citizen engagement workshop per study region.
- Local partners will provide full logistical and translation support to enable these workshops, while this task furnishes the know-how to ensure that these workshops are conducted following best practice and yield the most useful possible insights for the project.

Task 6.3 Development of storytelling and dissemination efforts (M8-M14, Lead: P5-SN, Co-lead: P7-AIRC, with contributions from all partners)

- Development of communication & dissemination supporting initiatives to raise the profile of the project within the participating territories and more widely
- Dissemination of exploitation reports. Annual report of completed and planned communication activities to consortium members, stakeholders and EC
- Good practice policy briefs on developing RRI institutional changes in an open and inclusive way at the territorial level

Task 6.4 Organisation of OpenRRIHub Final Summit for project partners (M30-M36, Lead: P5-SN, Co-lead: P1-ULEI, with contributions from all partners)

- Logistical organisation of a closing event for the project (M34), where the project can open the event for other participants. Venue: Leiden or Warsaw
- Define the programme with contributions from all the partners.

Deliverables

- D6.1 Communication, storytelling and dissemination strategy (M6)
- D6.2 Report Lessons learned report from stakeholder and citizen engagement collaborative workshops and related work (M16)
- D6.3 Storytelling strategy (M14)

Milestones

- M6.1 OpenRRIHub website (M8)
- M6.2 OpenRRIHub Final Summit (M34)

WORK PACKAGE NUMBER	7	LEAD BENEFICIARY	Futura Lab					
WORK PACKAGE TITLE	Broadening impact through communication, dissemination and exploitation							
Participant number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Short name of participant	ULEI	TCD	QA	IHS	SN	MFCR	AIRC	FL
Person months per participant	6	4	4	5	4	4	4	6
Start month	1	End month	36					

Objectives

The main objective of this WP is to develop a Sustainability and Legacy plans for OpenRRIHubs beyond the duration of the project:

- To develop and implement Sustainability & Legacy strategies
- To support the exploitation of OpenRRIHub results in coordination with WP6.
- To ensure the OpenRRI approach is incorporated at the governance level of the Territorial Partners.
- To produce a business model for the OpenRRIHubs beyond the duration of the project
- Scaffolding / Building the capacity of as institutions, to participate in pan-European and International R&I projects, programmes and networks.
- Contribution to SwafS legacy and advocacy for inclusion of RRI dimensions in the next EU framework programme Horizon Europe.

Description of work

This WP is led by P8-FL. All partners are involved in working together throughout the project in building the feasibility plans and business models for OpenRRIHubs

Task 7.1 Preparing the ground for the economic sustainability: develop material, resources and knowledge (M13-36, Lead: P8-FL)

- Develop a strategy to disseminate OpenRRIHub resources beyond the lifetime of the project.
- Develop a strategy to disseminate knowledge outcomes within established networks.
- Develop a strategy to integrate knowledge outcomes in relevant programmes run by the partners on a permanent basis.

Task 7.2 – From project to structure: promoting social RRI in and enhancing economic sustainability (M25-36, Lead: P8-FL, Co-lead: P4-IHS)

- Ensuring a sustainable framework for the OpenRRIHubs, which will include analysing assets, mission, legal and financial structure of each partner to identify a tailored legacy strategy.
- Development of individual social innovation models that include market study and segmentation, business plan, social impact, scaling strategies, funding and legal aspect.

Task 7.3 Synthesising SwafS knowledge base on best practice in territorial RRI to build long-term capacity (M13-36, Lead: ULEI)

- Development of a sustainable capacity-building tool that will provide a SwafS14-wide legacy synthesising learning from across all SwafS14 projects
- Support the advocacy efforts for the inclusion of RRI dimensions in the next EU framework programme Horizon Europe.

Deliverables

- D7.1 Sustainability and Legacy strategy (M24)
- D7.2 Social innovation models for OpenRRIHub sustainability (M30)
- D7.3 Roadmap/recommendations about SwafS-14 – Supporting the development of territorial Responsible Research and Innovation – legacy (M34)

WORK PACKAGE NUMBER	8	LEAD BENEFICIARY	ULEI					
WORK PACKAGE TITLE	Broadening impact through communication, dissemination and exploitation							
Participant number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Short name of participant	ULEI	TCD	QA	IHS	SN	MFCR	AIRC	FL
Person months per participant	0.5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Start month	1	End month	2					

Objectives

The objective is to set out the ‘ethics requirements’ and ensure compliance with the Horizon 2020 regulations.

Description of work

Task 8.1. Produce the necessary ‘ethics requirements’ documents in accordance to Horizon 2020 (M1-M36, Lead: PI-ULEI)

Deliverables

- D8.1 : H – Requirement No. 1 (M3)
- D8.2 : POPD – Requirement No. 2 (M3)
- D8.3 : GEN – Requirement No. 4 (M3)
- D8.4 : NEC – Requirement No. 6 (M3)

Table 3.1 c: List of Deliverables

DELIVERABLE No	DELIVERABLE NAME	WP No	SHORT NAME OF LEAD PARTICIPANT	TYPE	DISSEMINATION LEVEL	DELIVERY DATE
D1.1	OpenRRIHub Coordination Plan	1	ULEI	R	PU	M3
D1.2	First periodic report	1	ULEI	R	PU	M12
D1.3	Second periodic report	1	ULEI	R	PU	M24
D1.4	Final Report	1	ULEI	R	PU	M36
D2.1	Synthesis of best practices in application of MoRRI indicators	2	QA	R	PU	M6
D2.2	Lessons learned from citizen and engagement collaborative workshops and related work	2	QA	R	PU	M36
D2.3	RRI institutional change impact evaluation report	2	QA	R	PU	M36
D3.1	Report about each Territorial Partner organizational structure and stakeholders	3	IHS	R	PU	M6
D3.2	Report with stakeholder mapping in each Territorial Partner	3	IHS	R	PU	M8
D3.3	OpenRRIHub Blueprint, with the Structures, Strategies and Protocols for establishment of the OpenRRIHubs and OpenRRIHubMB	3	IHS	R	PU	M12
D4.1	Guidelines for co-designing Mission Roadmaps	4	ULEI	R	PU	M12
D4.2	Guidelines for the establishment of the R&I Open Calls	4	ULEI	R	PU	M15
D4.3	Guidelines for the co-assessment of R&I Mission-oriented pilot projects	4	ULEI	R	PU	M18
D4.4	Mission Roadmaps	4	ULEI	R	PU	M15
D4.5	Report about the co-assessment of the R&I Mission-oriented pilot projects	4	ULEI	R	PU	M36
D5.1	Toolkit for QH Open and Inclusive Engagement Strategy	5	TCD	R	PU	M12
D5.2	Training workshop about QH Engagement Strategy	5	TCD	R	PU	M13
D5.3	Publication (white paper, report, guide) with Lessons learnt from the mutual learning processes	5	TCD	R	PU	M34
D6.1	Communication, storytelling and dissemination strategy	6	SN	R	PU	M6
D6.2	Report Lessons learned report from stakeholder and citizen engagement	6	SN	R	PU	M16
D6.3	Storytelling strategy	6	SN	R	PU	M14
D7.1	Sustainability and Legacy strategy	7	FL	R	PU	M24
D7.2	Social innovation models for OpenRRIHub sustainability	7	FL	R	PU	M30
D7.3	Roadmap/recommendations about SwafS-14	7	FL	R	PU	M34
D8.1	H – Requirement No. 1	8	ULEI	R	CO	M3
D8.2	POPD – Requirement No. 2	8	ULEI	R	CO	M3
D8.3	GEN – Requirement No. 4	8	ULEI	R	CO	M3
D8.4	NEC – Requirement No. 6	8	ULEI	R	CO	M3

3.2. Management structure and procedures

3.2.1. Organization structure and decision-making

The structure overview for the OpenRRIHub organisation is summarised in Fig. 3.2a.

Project Officer:

The Project Officer appointed by the EU for the project is the link between the project and the European Commission. The Project Coordinator will be the contact point for the Project Officer. Any serious issue, risk, and crucial decision for the implementation of the project will be discussed with the Project Officer.

Project Board (including one representative of each partner organisation):

Each partner organisation will appoint one representative for the Project Board (PB). The PB will control the good progress of the project and advise the Project Coordinator (P1-ULEI) on the implementation. The PB is responsible for the project implementation in their organisation as agreed in the project description. They guarantee the involvement of Project Managers to implement the activities for the ones they engaged at the organisation level. The PB will virtually meet once every three months.

Advisory Board:

OpenRRIHub will establish an Advisory Board (AB) with at least 5 members. The task of the AB will be to both advise the PB on key aspects of the project and safeguard the project objectives. Each AB member will be selected for a special relevant expertise and will receive regular project reports from the coordinator. The appointment of members must be approved by the PB. Specific aspects of the project that will be safeguarded by ABs include Coordination with local businesses and industry (e.g.: Chamber of Commerce); coordination with local research organisations (e.g.: Universities), gender & diversity & equity expert, coordination with local school system and Independent Ethics Advisor. The AB will act as a review board a month before the official reviews by the European Commission. At least one AB member will act as external reviewers of the deliverables.

Project Manager (P1-ULEI):

The Project Manager (PM), appointed by the coordinator (P1-ULEI) has the responsibility of achieving project objectives according to the timeline and requirements described in the grant agreement. PM monitors the progress of each work package and makes sure that deadlines and objectives are met. The PM implements regular risk assessment, identifies potential issues, and proposes mitigations and solutions in relation to relevant partners. The PM reports and discusses EU management aspects and potentially serious issues with the Project Officer. The PM will attend monthly WP meetings and organise WP leaders meetings every two weeks.

Work package leaders (Work Package leader organisation: P1-ULEI, P2-TCD, P3-QA, P4-IHS, P6-SN, P8-FL):

The day to day management of the project will be implemented by the WP leaders, each responsible for the implementation of the activities described under their WPs and communication between partners involved in the same WP. The WP leaders ensure the delivery of WP activities on time and according to the objectives described in the grant agreement. They provide guidance and consultancy to the Project Manager when necessary. They monitor the progress and quality of the WP activities, ensure the submission of related deliverables on time, and collect data for the assessment of the activities of the associated WP. WP leaders should raise any issue or failure to achieve objectives to the Project Coordinator. WP leaders will meet once every two weeks under the initiative of the Project Coordinator. Each WP leader will organise monthly WP meeting involving all partners involved in their WP activities.

Local OpenRRIHub Managers and Local OpenRRIHub Management Boards:

The implementation of the project activities locally is managed by the local OpenRRIHub Manager (OpenRRIHubM). The OpenRRIHubM is responsible for specific activities in the project, e.g.: the implementation of activities at local levels. They are responsible for implementing these activities, collect data for assessment and reports, and support the dissemination activities of the project. The OpenRRIHubM manages the OpenRRIHub locally and organises the OpenRRIHub activities. OpenRRIHubMs will attend the relevant WP meetings. Partner Contacts and OpenRRIHub Managers will set up a local OpenRRIHub Management Board (OpenRRIHubMB) with representatives from the quadruple helix (government, academia, industry and civil society).

Fig 3.2a: OpenRRIHub organizational chart

Internal communication channels

All participants in the project will share common tools to ensure good communication between partners.

- **Project Management Software:** A project management system will be set up to be used for the day-to-day project communications (e.g. Basecamp). Here partners can open a private and secure communication space. The platform allows to start discussions involving different partners, keep track of discussions, share a calendar, and important documents. OpenRRIhub will also use an Innovation Management, eg.: Viima.
- **Main communication tool:** The project management software and emails about specific issues and relevant for groups of partners will be the regular communications exchange tool.
- **PB meetings:** The PM organises meetings with the PB every three months.
- **Advisory Board meetings:** The PM organises an Advisory Board meeting every 6 months.
- **WP leaders meetings:** The PM will organise WP leaders meetings every two weeks.
- **WP meetings:** The WP meetings will be organised by WP leaders and involve all partners involved in the activities of the related WP.
- **OpenRRIHub Managers meeting:** These meetings will be chaired by the PM and will involve the four OpenRRI-Hub managers. The PM will organise WP leaders meetings every two weeks.
- **Local OpenRRIHub Management Boards meetings:** The OpenRRIHubMB meetings will be organised by the OpenRRIHub managers every two months.

Other meetings: Extra meetings will be organised as necessary with small groups of partners. Decision-making and conflict resolution procedures The PB is the main decision-making body for OpenRRIHub. The day-to-day decision-making will be done by the PM in close consultation with WP leaders and the local OpenRRIHub Managers. The local decision-making by the local OpenRRIHubs will be done by the local OpenRRIHub Managers in close consultation with the local OpenRRIHub Management Boards. The potential for conflict in a project like OpenRRIHub is usually high because it involves individuals from different backgrounds and orientations working together to complete a complex task. The cause of conflict in team projects can be related to differences in values, attitudes, needs, expectations, perceptions, resources, and personalities. Any serious issue or potential risk for the implementation of the project should be raised by local OpenRRIHub Managers and Work Package leaders to the Project Manager. Any critical decision for the project will be discussed with the Project Board and raised to the Project Officer when necessary. Extraordinary consortium meetings can be organised in case of emergencies. The project will try to solve the conflict at the level of the conflict and escalate them to the next level if necessary. E.g.: If the conflict is at the WP level, the partners participating in that WP should try to solve it, but if an understanding is not, the WP leader should bring it up to the Project Manager, who should try to solve it at the Project Board level. At the level of the Project Board issues will be dealt with by the Advisory Board, and issues with the Advisory Board will be dealt with by the Project Board. Whenever possible, active listening – as a proven technique which managers can use to help resolve conflict – will be used. OpenRRIHub will use milestones to make regular checks in terms of implementation and budget with the European Union, Advisory board and local OpenRRIHub Management Boards. Table 3.2a provides an overview of the planned milestones.

Table 3.2 a: List of milestones

MILESTONE No	MILESTONE NAME	RELATED WORK PACKAGES	DUE DATE (IN MONTH)	MEANS OF VERIFICATION
M1.1	Consortium Meeting #1	1	2	R
M1.2	Consortium Meeting #2	1	20	R
M2.1	Evaluation frameworks	2	9	R
M3.1	OpenRRIHub Blueprint	3	6	R
M4.1	Selected R&I Mission-oriented pilot projects	4	18	R
M5.1	Mutual Learning visits and calls for mutual learning	5	14	R
M6.1	OpenRRIHub website	6	8	Website
M6.2	OpenRRIHub Final Summit	6	34	R

3.2.2. Risk mitigation

In the following table 3.2b, the consortium estimates the potential risks that could become critical for implementation for the project and addresses them by proposing mitigation measures. This initial risk assessment will be used as a baseline for potential risks that could appear during the implementation of the project. Risk assessment will be performed at every step of the project and managed as to anticipate and minimise potential issues that may arise. Any identified issue that could become critical for the project achievement of its objectives will be raised and discussed with the Project Officer.

Table 3.2b: Critical risks for implementation

DESCRIPTION OF RISK (INDICATE LEVEL OF LIKELIHOOD: LOW/MEDIUM/HIGH)	WORK PACKAGE(S) INVOLVED	PROPOSED RISK-MITIGATION MEASURES
Consortium partner withdraws. (Low)	1	If a partner withdraws, a suitable replacement will be found within the consortium and if necessary outside the consortium.
A partner coordinator or manager withdraws or is incapacitated. (Medium)	All	Relevant partner needs to find a replacement within a month. If needed, relevant tasks will be transferred between partners. The Project Board involving representatives of each organisation are responsible for the good involvement of their organisation in the project.
The project failed to meet a milestone or deliverable (Medium)	All	When the situation appears, the coordinator discusses the reasons for failure with the involved partners and reports them to the Project Officer. When necessary, adapted corrective actions will be taken.
Insufficient reporting by partners to meet the deliverables (Low)	1	All partners will assign experienced project managers and have a supporting administrating department or staff. Within the respective WPs, the different partners involved will have the necessary information to fulfil the task, if necessary
Ineffective internal communication tools or approaches (Low)	1	The Coordinator will establish internal communication tools applying the principles of good design, usability and interaction design, and will monitor their effectiveness in consultation with all the partners. This will mitigate risks linked to bad users' and low level of usability.
A reduced interest of the target group on participation in project activities (Medium)	5	The activities in the local community will start on M6, with community consultation events: this way the project will guarantee the participation of all target groups in the initial phase. If interest is reduced, the community will be consulted, and appropriate actions will be taken.

Restrictions/disruption due to COVID-19 (medium)

All

Given the global uncertainty arising from the COVID-19 pandemic, all partners will have contingency plans for remote work where travel and face-to-face is unavailable. If there are still restrictions at that stage — state of the art online versions of all project workshops can be offered which aligns with the expertise of the partners involved.

3.3. Consortium as a whole

The lead partner, Leiden University (P1-ULEI), has several years of solid experience running large-scale Science, Technology and Innovation (STI) and RRI-based projects at national, European and global level through the coordination of several H2020 projects. Trinity College Dublin (P2-TCD) has extensive experience in running STI, community building and stakeholder-based activities through Science Gallery Dublin. Qualia Analytics (P3-QA) has wide expertise in research and evaluation, and on developing stakeholder engagement and RRI integration. Impact Hub Syracuse (P4-IHS) is part of the global network (IH) of hubs that foster entrepreneurship, idea incubation and business development. Science Now (P5-SC) is a team of experienced producers, scientists, artists and communicators. Futura Lab (P8-FL) is an innovation laboratory, part of Aruba's Government, with extensive expertise in the development of human-centred innovation plans. The territorial partners – Local Governments, such as Municipalities of Leiden and Den Haag (P1-ULEI), Municipality of Figueira de Castelo Rodrigo (P6-MFCR), Regional Government Organisations, such as AIR Centre, Azores (P9-AIRC) and the National Governments Institution – Government of Aruba/Futura Lab (P8-FL) will co-develop OpenRRIHubs, collaboration hubs for research, innovation and community development rooted in RRI, and evidence-based environmental decision-making through collaborations among policy makers, education providers, enterprises, research institutes, and civil society. OpenRRIHubs consortium includes 8 partners with complementary skills, expertise and experience to implement RRI in their territories through innovative processes. The 8 partners are two research universities (P1-ULEI, P2-TCD), one of which with formal links with local Municipalities and host of the EuroScience Open Forum 2022 (P1-ULEI), three small and medium enterprises (P3-QA, P4-IHS, P5-SN), one municipality (P6-MFCR), one regional government (P9-AIRC) and one national government (P8-FL). OpenRRIHubs will be implemented at local government level (urban areas like Leiden and The Hague – P1-ULEI and rural like P6-MFCR), regional government level (e.g.: Azores, P9-AIRC) and at the National level, with P8-FL, an Overseas countries and Territories (OCT, Aruba) and with the cooperation commitment from dozens relevant local stakeholders (local/regional governments, universities and research organisations, industry, SMEs, enterprises, civil society organizations and actors). All local OpenRRIHubs (P1, P6, P7, P8) will work closely with policy makers, education providers, enterprises, research institutes, and civil society, who have already expressed their commitment to the project.

3.4. Resources to be committed

From the implementation point of view, OpenRRIHubs will rely on highly experienced and qualified staff (Section 4). Summary of staff previous experience and skills are described in Section 4, the summary of the staff effort per WP is on table 3.4a. The explanation of the use of all resources is on table 3.4b.

Table 3.4a: Summary of staff effort

	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8	TOTAL PERSON-MONTHS PER PARTICIPANT
P1-ULEI	5	4	7	7	7	5	6	0.5	41.5
P2-TCD	2	6	3	3	12	3	4	0	33
P3-QA	2	14	3	3	5	3	4	0	34
P4-IHS	2	3	14	4	4	3	5	0	35
P5-SN	2	3	3	3	3	16	4	0	34
P6-MFCR	2	4	7	7	7	3	4	0	34
P8-AIRC	2	4	7	7	7	3	4	0	34
P9-FL	2	4	7	7	7	3	6	0	36
TOTAL PERSON-MONTHS	19	42	51	41	52	39	37	0.5	281.5

P1-ULEI	COST (€)	JUSTIFICATION
Travel	14 000	€1000 x 10 trips in Europe (per trip: flight €400 EUR and €600 EUR for 5-day accomodation and food); €4000 = 2 trips to Aruba (per trip: Flight €1000 + €1000, 5-day accomodation and food). Justification: Two consortium meetings, 8 mutual learning visits to partners and participation in two relevant conferences (e.g.: ECSITE)
Equipment	4 500	€3000 for 2 laptops (€1500 each) and €1500 software costs (e.g.: Basecamp, Slack, GSuite or innovation management tools like: Viima)
Other goods and services	19 000	€15000 Logistical costs (venue, transportation, catering) for 10 community events (from hackathons to activation events (€1500 each); €1500 for production of local communication; €2500 for advocacy costs (meetings and production of policy briefings)

TOTAL **37 500**

P2-TCD	COST (€)	JUSTIFICATION
Travel	11 000	€7000: 7 trips in Europe (per trip: flight €400 EUR and €600 EUR for 5-day accomodation and food); €4000: 2 trips to Aruba (per trip: Flight €1000 + €1000, 5-day accomodation and food) Justification: Two consortium meetings, 4 mutual learning visits to partners and participation in one relevant conferences (e.g.: ESOF)
Equipment	2 000	€1500 for one laptop and €500 software costs (e.g.: GSuite, SPSS)
Other goods and services	3 000	€1500 Open Access Fees; €1500 for meeting costs (venues, catering)

TOTAL **16 000**

P3-QA	COST (€)	JUSTIFICATION
Travel	11 000	€7000: 7 trips in Europe (per trip: flight €400 EUR and €600 EUR for 5-day accomodation and food); €4000: 2 trips to Aruba (per trip: Flight €1000 + €1000, 5-day accomodation and food) Justification: Two consortium meetings, 4 mutual learning visits to partners and participation in one relevant conferences (e.g.: ESOF; World Science Forum)
Equipment	2 000	€2000 high capacity laptop for running data analysis software
Other goods and services	7 500	€3000 Open Access Fees; €1500 for meeting costs (venues, catering); €3000 specialist analysis software and development cost for adaptations of existing software solutions.

TOTAL **20 500**

P4-IHS	COST (€)	JUSTIFICATION
Travel	11 000	€7000: 7 trips in Europe (per trip: flight €400 EUR and €600 EUR fo 4 5-day accomodation and food); €4000: 2 trips to Aruba (per trip: Flight €1000 + €1000, 5-day accomodation and food). Justification: Two consortium meetings, 4 mutual learning visits to partners and participation in one relevant conferences (e.g.: ESOF)
Equipment	2 000	€1500 for one laptop and €500 software costs (e.g.: GSuite)
Other goods and services	6 000	€1500 for meeting costs (venues, catering) €4500 social innovation consultancy costs

TOTAL **19 000**

P5-SN	COST (€)	JUSTIFICATION
Travel	11 000	€7000: 7 trips in Europe (per trip: flight €400 EUR and €600 EUR for 5-day accomodation and food); €4000: 2 trips to Aruba (per trip: Flight €1000 + €1000, 5-day accomodation and food) Justification: Two consortium meetings, 4 mutual learning visits to partners and participation in one relevant conferences (e.g.: ESOF)
Equipment	2 000	€1500 for one laptop and €500 software costs (e.g.: GSuite and Adobe CC)
Other goods and services	13 500	€8500 development and implementation of a digital media presence (website, social media with a focus on specific target groups such as R&I and Governance): €5000 Production of communication resources (e.g.: white papers, finding reports)
TOTAL	26 500	

P6-MFCR	COST (€)	JUSTIFICATION
Travel	9 000	€7000: 7 trips in Europe (per trip: flight €400 EUR and €600 EUR for 5-day accomodation and food); €2000: 1 trips to Aruba (Flight €1000 + €1000, 4/5-day accomodation and food). Justification: Two consortium meetings, 3 mutual learning visits to partners and participation in one relevant conferences (e.g.: ESOF)
Equipment	2 000	€1500 for one laptop and €500 software costs (e.g.: GSuite)
Other goods and services	16 500	€15000 Logistical costs (venue, transportation, catering) for 10 community events (from hackathons to activation events, €1500 each) ; €1500 for production of local communication materials.
TOTAL	27 500	

P7-AIRC	COST (€)	JUSTIFICATION
Travel	9 000	€7000: 7 trips in Europe (per trip: flight €400 EUR and €600 EUR for 5-day accomodation and food); €2000: 1 trips to Aruba (Flight €1000 + €1000, 4/5-day accomodation and food) Justification: Two consortium meetings, 3 mutual learning visits to partners and participation in one relevant conferences (e.g.: ESOF)
Equipment	2 000	€1500 for one laptop and €500 software costs (e.g.: GSuite)
Other goods and services	16 000	€15000 Logistical costs (venue, transportation, catering) for 10 community events (from hackathons to activation events, €1500 each); €1500 for production of local communication.
TOTAL	27 000	

P8-FL	COST (€)	JUSTIFICATION
Travel	16 000	€16000: 10 trips in Europe (per trip: flight €1000 EUR and €600 EUR for 5-day accomodation and food). Two consortium meetings, 7 mutual learning visits to partners and participation in one relevant EU conference (e.g.: ESOF)
Equipment	2 000	€1500 for one laptop and €500 software costs (e.g.: GSuite)
Other goods and services	19 000	€15000 Logistical costs (venue, transportation, catering) for 10 community events (from hackathons to activation events, €1500 each); €1500 for production of local communication. €2500 for advocacy costs (meetings and production of policy briefings)
TOTAL	37 000	